

Agrometeorology of Wheat in Himachal Pradesh state of India

Rajendra Prasad, V.U.M. Rao, Ch. Srinivasa Rao

CSK HPKV, Palampur, HP
and
Central Research Institute for Dryland Agriculture
Hyderabad
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CONTRIBUTORS

Name	Designation
D. Badiyala	Principal Scientist & Head, Department of Agronomy
S.C. Negi	Chief Scientist , Department of Agronomy
Ashwani Basandrai	Scientist In-charge, Wheat and Rice Research Station, Malan
Pawan K. Sharma	Principal Scientist, Department of Entomology
Sandeep Manuja	Principal Scientist, Wheat and Rice Research Station, Malan
Vijay Rana	Principal Scientist, Wheat and Rice Research Station, Malan

	Name	Designation
AICRPAM NICRA Staff	Anupam Sharma	Research Associate
	Jyoti	Senior Research Fellow
	Parveen Kumar	Data Entry Operator
	Ajay Kumar	Data Entry Operator
	Meera Devi Chandel	Data Entry Operator

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K. K. Katoch, Ph.D.

Vice Chancellor

Chaudhary Sarwan Kumar Himachal Pradesh Krishi Vishvavidyalaya

Palampur - 176062

FOREWORD

Wheat is one of the major crops grown in Himachal Pradesh. Cheap and adequate availability of wheat flour and its other products to consumers is possible only if spectacular growth story of wheat production and productivity continues. The climate and soils of the state are largely suitable for the cultivation of wheat and also due to the advantage of wider adaptability; this crop is grown in almost all the districts of the state. The major districts accounting for over 99 per cent area and production under wheat are Kangra, Mandi, Hamirpur, Una, Sirmaur, Bilaspur, Shimla, Solan, Kullu and Chamba. Crop is largely grown under rain fed conditions. Inadequate rains during sowing time of wheat (mid- October to mid- December) result in inadequate soil moisture which causes poor germination and seedling growth of the crop. Shallow coarse textured soils with undulating topography have poor soil moisture storage capacity leading to poor moisture availability during the season for all rain fed crops. Rainfall being inadequate and erratically distributed, the critical stages of this crop lack sufficient soil moisture. Mid hills encounters low air and soil temperature conditions resulting in stunted growth during initial phases of crop growth. Weather, therefore, takes a heavy toll on this crop. Below optimum use of fertilizers in the wake of inadequate moisture availability are some of the major issues attracting attention of scientists and research managers during recent years. The All India Coordinated Research Project on Agrometeorology, Palampur Centre sanctioned in 1995 and started basic work during 1998 with the joining of Dr. Rajendra Prasad, as Principal Investigator of this project. Since then ample work on the Agrometeorological aspect of wheat has been carried out. The documentation of this work will really be helpful to identify the critical gaps to plan the future research programme on this valuable crop and also to address the issues of sustainable production of this crop through adequate weather proofing strategies.

I congratulate Dr. Rajendra Prasad, Principal Agrometeorologist and his team for bringing out bulletin “The Agrometeorology of wheat in Himachal Pradesh state of India”. I sincerely hope that this publication will be of immense use to the research scientists, farm managers and above all to the students.

K.K. Katoch
Vice – Chancellor

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AUTHORS

CHAPTER 1

Introduction

1.1 Origin and history

Agriculture came into existence in 7500 BC when cultivation of wheat and barley was started. Wheat (*Triticumaestivum* L. emend Thell.) known as king of cereals and is amongst the first cereals domesticated by hunter- gatherer societies of South West Asia. Since domestication, its acreage expanded dramatically and now occupying the position of widest geographic coverage in the world.

1.2 Importance of the crop

The grains of this crop possess unique gluten content and associated bread making properties. Wheat grain contains protein 7-18%, mineral matter (ash), 1.5-2%, lipids (fat) 1.5-2%, starch 60-68 %, cellulose (crude fibre) 2-2.5% and moisture 8-18% (NIIR Board of Consultants and Engineers, 2006). It also contains 2-3 % germ, 13-17% bran and 80-85% mealy endosperm. Bran contains 53% fibre and 16% protein and carbohydrate (Belderok *et al.*, 2000). The flour of grains of this crop is used to prepare *Chapatti*, *Prantha* and *Biscuits Puri* and *Bhature* from maida, semolina, macaroni products, wheat germ oil and wheat bran etc as feed. It is also widely used in industries; wheat stalks in geotextiles, straw particle boards, starch as adhesive, hair conditioners and moisturizers, liquid laundry detergents, water soluble inks, starch replacing fat in desserts and milk replacers.

1.3 Adaptation and geographical distribution

It is grown near the equator as well as 60degree North and 40 degree South latitude. The productivity increases with latitude. It is low in south and high in north. In the northern Hemisphere the pole ward limit of economic wheat production corresponds with May isotherm of 10°C. It can be grown 0-3660 m above mean sea level. The total world area under wheat is 222.6 million hectares with an annual production of 716.1 million tonnes with the productivity of 3.22 t/ha (USDA, 2013-14).Green revolution in India was essentially a wheat revolution, the triplegene dwarf Mexican wheat replaced the traditional Emmer-wheat (*Triticumdicoccum*), Macaroni wheat (*T. durum*) and dwarf wheat (*T. spherococcum*) and now most of the wheats are *T. aestivum*occupying production share of over 95%. Common wheat/Bread wheat (*Tritium aestivum* L. emend Thell.) is most commonly grown in North

India (entire North western Plain Zone) and far east and eastern India (i.e., entire North Eastern Plain Zone). This wheat is also grown in major areas of Central Zone, Peninsular Zone and hilly regions of India. In India, wheat is second most important food crop, next only to rice. It is grown in an area of 31.2 million hectares with the production of 95.9 million tonnes and productivity of 3075 kg/ha (Economic Survey, 2014-15). It has been estimated that India will need at least 109 million tonnes of wheat by 2020 as against present production of 93.9 million tonnes from an area of 29.90 m ha with productivity of 31.40 q/ha (The ministry of EFCC, Government of India, 2012).

The spring wheat is characterized by shorter period of growth; they mature in 5-6 or 7-8 months depending upon thermal regime. They do not require very low temperature during early period of growth. Spring wheat occupies major area in India as well as in Himachal Pradesh. The varieties with long period of growth and with greater requirement of low temperature at early stages of growth are sown in September/October and pass through severe winter covered by snow. They ear in spring and mature during summer months (June-July), thus completing life cycle in 10-11 months. These are called as winter wheat. The principal areas in Himachal Pradesh where winter wheat is grown are the Spiti valley of Lahaul and Spiti and Dodra Kwar areas of Chamba district. The exact area is however not exactly known. The young seedlings of this wheat after emergence are grazed by the sheep and goat for about one month and it acts as a very palatable and scarce fodder for these animals. After one month snow covers the area and wheat undergoes winter dormancy. When the temperature starts rising, it pick up the growth after the month of March and grows well to give good yield.

Himachal Pradesh shares nearly 10 percent of the acreage and 9 percent of the total production of wheat in India. The productivity of wheat in this state is around 28.4 tonnes/ha with an area of 0.36 million hectare and production of 10.23 million tonnes (DEST, Government of Himachal Pradesh, 2012). Though, many states including Himachal Pradesh have witnessed spectacular growth in production and productivity, which has made country not only self-sufficient but also for exporting surplus wheat. There is need to further increase production (or at least arrest and maintain the production of Himachal Pradesh till 2020 possibly by weather proofing it from weather vagaries) to fulfil the requirement of exploding population, maintenance of adequate buffer stock and to meet out demand for processing industries.

1.4 Climatic and soil requirement

The productivity of a crop is at the mercy of prevailing climate/ weather right from tillage of land and plating the crop to harvest, storage, marketing the farm produce. This uncertainty is considered to be giving about 50 per cent variability in annual crop production, it being of high magnitude in border areas of agro-climatic zones. The final yield of a crop, therefore, depends on all that has happened to it during growth prior to harvest. It is conversion of the input factors of the physical environment that gives the economic harvestable produce. Even what happens during harvest and after harvest till the produce is fit for consumption is of paramount importance. The adverse conditions during this period can outweigh the whole favourable growth and development period of a crop. The environmental factors are changing every hour/day in magnitude and thus are of importance for day-to-day adjustment, though difficult to do so. The atmospheric factors fluctuate much more abruptly (than soil factors) except for day duration which is the only reliable parameter of the climate.

1.4.1 Climate

Climate is a carrier wave and weather is an irregularity on this wave hence an important factor of any habitat which helps in interpreting the reason of poor or bumper crop harvests. Temperature and precipitation make the general backbone of the carrier wave hence concern us the most. These largely determine what shall be the staple crops of that region. (J.R. Kakde, 1985). Wheat possesses wider adaptability and is the staple food for over 35 per cent of the world population. Wheat can tolerate severe cold and snow and resume growth with the setting in of warm weather in spring. (www.farmer.gov.in)

1.4.2 Soil

Soils with a clay loam or loam texture, good structure and moderate water holding capacity are ideal for wheat cultivation. Soil should be neutral in its reaction. Heavy soil with good drainage is suitable for wheat cultivation under dry conditions. These soils absorb and retain rain water well. Heavy soils with poor structure and poor drainage are not suitable as wheat is sensitive to water logging. Wheat can be successfully grown on lighter soils provided their water and nutrient holding capacity are improved (www.farmer.gov.in).

Himachal Pradesh has a consortium of soils ranging from sandy skeletal to fine loamy soils. Entisols occupy the largest area (51.3%) followed by Inceptisols (19.8%), Mollisols (0.8%) and Alfisols (0.4%). The rock outcrops and glaciers also occupy a major chunk (27.7%) of the total geographic area of the state. Among the Entisols, the Udorthents

constitute the major part (33.5%) followed by Cryorthents (14.9%), Ustifluvents (2%), Udifluvents (1.2%), Ustor-thents (0.5%) and Ustipsamments (0.1%). Among Inceptisols, Eutrochrepts occupy highest area (17.2%) followed by Ustochrepts (1.5%), Dystrichrepts (0.8%) and Cryochrepts (0.3%).

The area of greater Himalayas represents most of the cold desert of the state covering Lahaul and Spiti, Pangi tehsil of Chamba and high reaches of Kinnaur. It is composed of sedimentary rocks in Lahaul and Spiti area besides granities, granite-gneisses and metamorphic rocks which is composed of 47.1 per cent of the total geographic area of the state. Soils are mainly stony, coarse-loamy and fine-loamy. Soils of major part of the state being lesser Himalayas (31 per cent) comprising districts of Kinnaur, Shimla, Solan, Kullu, Mandi, Chamba and Northern parts of Kangra and Sirmaur districts are mainly coarse loamy and fine loamy. Shiwalik area of the state includes parts of district Kangra, Hamirpur, Bilaspur, Una, Sirmaur and Southern parts of Solan districts which comprises 20 percent of the total area and soils are mainly sandy, sandy-skeletal, loamy-skeletal, coarse loamy and fine loamy with moderate to severe erosion. Alluvial plains (0.6 per cent) of rivers Beas, Satluj, Solan and tributaries of Yamuna river in districts Bilaspur, Una, Kangra and Sirmaur has stratified, coarse-loamy and fine-loamy with slight erosion and slight stoniness.

Soil depth suggests the volume of the soil which the root can exploit for obtaining their nutrients and water for growth. Depth of the soil controls the effective rooting depth of plants, and in accord with its texture, mineralogy and gravel content, the capacity of the soil profile to hold water and supply plant nutrients is determined.

About 35.2 per cent of the area of Himachal Pradesh has medium deep (50-100 cm) soils followed by 18.0 per cent shallow (50 cm). Afforestation with coniferous species on high altitudes and deciduous species on mid and lower altitudes, graded bunding with plantation of climatically adapted fruit crops along contours and cultivation of *Kharif* millets suggested for soils having shallow to medium depth. About 17.9 percent area is covered with deep soils (100 cm) which is suitable for growing wheat, maize and rice.

Whether the climate and soils of entire state are highly suitable for wheat or not, but due to the advantage of wider adaptability, this crop is grown in almost all the districts of the state. The main districts are Kangra, Mandi, Hamirpur, Una, Sirmaur, Bilaspur, Shimla, Solan, Kullu and Chamba which account for over 99 per cent area and production under wheat.

Chapter 2

Agro-climatic characteristics

Characterization of crop growing environment is a pre-requisite in crop planning and evolving strategies to overcome climate/weather induced changes in the meso/micro climate. Anomalies in climate variables need to be properly understood to make agricultural sector resilient. Thus, historic data on climatic variables was analysed using appropriate statistical tools (produced by NARS (National Agriculture Research System) and Weathercock 15 of CRIDA (Central Research Institute of Dryland Agriculture) enabling the development of location specific technologies/adaptive strategies. The analysis carried out by AICRPAM, Palampur centre on the agro-climatic characterization of wheat growing environments is reported hereunder:

2.1 Normal weekly temperature and rainfall

Normal weekly maximum and minimum temperature for Akrot, Bajaura, Berthin, Dhaulakuan, Kangra, Malan, Palampur, Salooni and Shimla (Annexure 1). The maximum and minimum temperature varied between 11.6 (Shimla) to 37.0 °C (Akrot) and 0.3 (Bajaura) to 21.1 °C (Akrot), respectively.

Normal weekly rainfall and rainy days for 40 stations are given in Annexure 1a & 1b. The rainfall varied between 0.0 (Chachiot) to 45.5 mm (Nurpur). The rainy days varied between 0 to 1 day per week.

2.2 Normal monthly temperature and rainfall

On the monthly basis, the mean maximum temperature as an average of nine stations (31.6°C) is observed to be highest during May and lowest (17.1 °C) during January (Annexure 1c). April and May months are the warmest at all the nine stations of the state. At station level Akrot in district Una was the warmest station (37.8 °C) followed by Dhaulakuan in Sirmaur district (36.9 °C) and Berthin in Bilaspur district (35.6 °C). Salooni and Shimla are the cooler stations (21.1 to 25.0 °C) as far as the maximum temperature is concerned.

On average monthly basis, January was the coolest month (4.7°C) followed by December (5.8°C) and February (6.5°C) whereas the warmest month is May (16.8°C) followed by October (13.6°C) and April (13.0°C) (Annexure 1c). But temperatures are high at Salooni (8.1°C) and is lowest at Bajaura (1.0°C) followed by Berthin and Shimla (3.6°C). Information on the monthly rainfall for a location is helpful for crop planning,

cultivar selection, run off estimation, determining crop water needs, and for designing watersheds and ultimately irrigation system. The rainfall distribution on monthly basis with the associated variability for different stations is presented in Annexure 1d. November is the driest month in the state (18 mm) followed by October (30 mm), December (34 mm) and April (45 mm). However, difference in the rainfall of October and December is just of 4mm. One of the stations, Salooni receives highest *rabi* season rainfall during October to April (95 to 198 mm).

Therefore, it is not the total amount of rainfall on a monthly basis that is vital, but the number of rainy days in a month determines the distribution of rain, this is what matters the most. High variability in rainfall is norm rather than exception. District-wise average number of rainy days on a monthly basis are furnished in the Annexure 1e. It may be observed that lowest frequency is noticed during November (1 day) followed by October and December (1 day each). The months of January, April and May have same frequencies (4 days) and February and March (5 days). Amongst the stations, most of the stations showed similar number of rainy days during the months of November and December. Twenty four stations showed single rainy day during November whereas rests of the stations witnessed 2 to 5 rainy days. Rainfall during *rabi* season is generally substantial and on an average the state receives 395 mm rainfall in 27 days.

2.3 Moisture and temperature at sowing and critical stages

The largest quantities of best wheat's are produced in areas favoured with cool and moist weather during a fairly long growing period followed by a dry and warm weather to enable the grains to ripen properly. Wheat is basically a temperate plant, grown in summer season in temperate regions and winter or *rabi* season in the sub tropics. Wheat can withstand temperatures from extremely low to fairly high (Lenka, 1998; Kakde, 1985). The optimum temperature range for ideal germination of wheat seed is 20-25 °C though the seeds can germinate in the temperature range 3.5 to 35°C. Rains just after sowing hamper germination and encourage seedling blight. Areas with a warm and damp climate are not suited for wheat crop. During the heading and flowering stages, excessively high or low temperatures and drought are harmful. Cloudy weather, with high humidity and low temperatures is conducive for rust attack. The temperature conditions at the time of grain filling and development are very crucial for yield. Temperatures above 25°C during this period tend to depress grain weight. When temperatures are high, too much energy lost through the process of

transpiration by the plants and the reduced residual energy results in poorer grain formation and lower yields. Thus, wheat plant requires about 14-15°C optimum average temperature at the time of ripening. Wheat is mainly a *rabi* (winter) season crop in India (www.farmer.gov.in).

2.4 Crop growing environment

All efforts to obtain profitable crop production involve improving adaptations of either crop to the environment or environment to the crop. Either of two is practiced. Agrometeorology of the crop aims to solve the both. Detailed weather-wise crop management of wheat is given in Annexure 2. The resultant effect of genotype-environment- management interaction is actual harvested productivity which may be 45-50 % of the potential yield. The actual productivity under field conditions is influenced by host of unpredictable factors. This productivity is measured by total biomass or harvestable produce. Proper knowledge of plant growth characteristics, factors affecting growth and their relationships is essential for any substantial success in crop production technology. The general cardinal values of temperature for wheat though were suggested to be: minimum, 0-5°C, optimum: 25-31°C, and maximum: 31 to 37°C vary considerably and appear to be region specific. A mean daily temperature of 15-20°C is optimum for growth and development (Lenka, 1998).

2.5 Crop weather Calendar

The Crop Calendar is a tool that provides timely information about crop stage and condition of the crop. It contains information on planting, important phenophases and harvesting periods of locally adapted crops in specific agro-ecological zone or a district to be specific. The detail information regarding the wheat crop phenology was collected from the AICRPAM APR for variety VL-907 for five years (2010-11 to 2014-15). During this period, periodic field scouting and agro climatic field surveys were also carried out to further fine tune the phenology of this crop/variety. Accordingly the crop weather calendar was designed. The specific details provided by the AICRPAM coordinating unit in a capacity building program on “Analysis of data collected in AICRPAM, crop weather relations and documentation of results etc.” organized at CRIDA, Hyderabad during 28th July to 06th Aug, 2015 were also included to come up with district wise uniform crop weather calendar of wheat. After the successful emergence and under non- limiting input supplies, the crop growth phases are the subject of weather conditions alone viz., ambient temperature, rainfall, relative humidity, BSS and radiation etc. The upper most portion of the calendar indicates the normal weather requirements during the every week of the crop

growth period (Fig. 2.1). The middle portion shows the duration of important growth phases like sowing, seedling, vegetative stage, heading and anthesis, grain filling and physiological maturity in weeks. Emergence & seedling establishment phase took 4-5 weeks, tillering (5-6 weeks), heading to anthesis (9-10 weeks), grain filling to soft dough (2-3 weeks) and hard dough to maturity (5-6 weeks). At the bottom, pest and diseases of the crop are shown with the duration of life cycle of most important pest, wheat aphids and the disease, yellow rust along with their favourable weather conditions. This information on the weather parameters would be highly beneficial in issuing weather based agro advisories and weather warning of expected weather and its associated adverse effect on the crop.

The crop enjoyed 13.0-30.5 °C and 2.5-18.0°C maximum and minimum temperature respectively, 35-85% RH, 5-40 mm rainfall/week, 6-36 mm/week evaporation, 3-10 hrs/day, BSS20 and yielded 44 q/ ha at Palampur. Though, lot of experience and information has been used in preparation of the crop calendar still addition to the already complied information is required to be aided to improve research and agriculture operations at regional and national levels. Which can be done by routine recording of data on phenological events every year otherwise, would be lost forever if not recorded.

Fig 2.1 Crop Weather Calendar

Crop : Irrigated Wheat

Duration: Long (180-190 days)

State: Himachal Pradesh

District: Kangra

Climatic normals	Std Week	October			November				December				January					February					March				April				May		
		42	43	44	45	46	47	48	49	50	51	52	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12	13	14	15	16	17	18	19		
Parameter		25	24	23	22	21	20	19	19	18	17	16	15	15	15	15	16	16	17	17	18	20	21	22	23	24	26	27	28	29	29		
Tmax (°C)		13	12	12	11	10	9	7	7	7	6	5	5	5	5	6	6	7	7	8	9	10	11	12	13	14	15	17	17	18			
Tmin (°C)		61	62	59	59	58	57	60	56	58	58	61	61	63	63	63	63	64	61	60	57	58	56	56	51	50	50	48	47	49			
RHm (%)		47	47	46	47	45	45	47	45	49	48	50	51	50	54	51	50	54	53	49	48	45	47	47	45	41	39	39	37	37	39		
RHe (%)		3	3	3	4	3	3	3	3	3	3	3	3	3	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	4		
WS (kmph)		North easterly/west south westerly											Easterly northeasterly/west south westerly									East north easterly/west south westerly											
WD		8	8	8	7	7	7	7	7	6	6	6	6	6	5	6	6	6	5	6	6	6	6	6	6	6	7	7	8	7	8	8	8
BSS (hr/day)		37	33	33	28	34	40	30	37	24	25	28	25	30	25	25	22	25	26	27	23	24	32	33	35	31	41	35	48	39	35		
S. Rad (MJ/m2/day)		27	25	25	24	23	22	19	17	16	15	17	13	14	13	14	16	16	17	19	22	25	26	28	31	35	38	42	44	47	48		
EVP (mm/week)		6	3	3	4	4	3	6	4	12	9	19	16	20	20	31	16	26	36	25	28	19	27	31	15	15	13	13	12	15	18		
Rain (mm/week)		0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	2	1	1	1	1	2	1	1	1	1	1	1	1		
Rainy days/week		North easterly/west south westerly											Easterly northeasterly/west south westerly									East north easterly/west south westerly											

Phenophase-wise weather for better yield	Phenophase Duration (days)	Emergence & seedling establishment (32-35)	Tillering (40-42)	Heading & anthesis (65-70)	Grain –filling & soft dough (18-21)	Hard dough to maturity (40-42)	
	Tmax (°C)	19.5-25.5	15.5-21.5	13.0-18.0	20.5-22.0	23.0-30.5	
	Tmin (°C)	6.5-12.5	3.0-7.0	2.5-7.0	9.0-11.0	11.0-18.0	
	RHm (%)	60-85	65-80	65-85	60-65	50-65	
	RHe (%)	40-65	40-55	50-70	45-50	35-65	
	WS (kmph)	5.0-5.5	5.2-5.8	5.0-7.0	7.0-8.0	6.0-7.0	
	WD	North easterly/south westerly		Easterly northeasterly/west south westerly			East north easterly/west south westerly
	BSS (hr/day)	6-8	6-9	3-6	5-7	5-10	
	S. Rad (MJ/m2/day)	30-33	24-45	17-33	32-35	31-48	
	EVP (mm/week)	12-18	9-11	6-12	14-16	19-36	
Rain (mm/week)	8-10	5-10	28-30	35-40	15-20		
Rainy days/week	1	1	2	3	2		
Congenial weather for pest & diseases	Wheat Aphid	T max 12-24°C, T min 2-10°C, RHm 65-90%, RHe 45-80% , BSS 2.0-9.0 hr/day					
	Yellow Rust			T max 10-20°C Rainfall < 100 mm			

All India Coordinated Research Project on Agrometeorology, CSK HPKV, PALAMPUR

2.6 Spatio-temporal changes in area, production and productivity of wheat

The climate and soils of the state are largely suitable for wheat crop. Due to the advantage of wider adaptability, this crop is grown in almost all the districts of the state. The main districts Kangra, Mandi, Hamirpur, Una, Sirmaur, Bilaspur, Shimla, Solan, Kullu and Chamba, account for over 99 per cent area and production under wheat. The productivity has been increased during the recent years. The spatio-temporal changes in area and productivity were worked out using 19 years data (1995-96 to 2013-14) and are presented in Fig 2.2.

Fig 2.2 Area and productivity during 1995-96 to 2013-14

2.7 Potential areas of wheat production in Himachal Pradesh

Productivity gap analysis is done to quantify the difference between the potential productivity of a crop in a region and its productivity at farm level. This analysis is generally done using experimental data, here an attempt is made to identify the regions of high productivity and low productivity retaining heterogeneity encountered at district level. The identification of the production constraints will help bring all the zones to higher productivity levels by developing suitable strategies to improve the production at farm level. The criteria adopted for demarcation of potential areas are based on area as well as productivity of the crop. Low, medium & high area were less than 15000 ha, 15000-25000 ha & more than 25000 ha, respectively and low, medium & high productivity were less than 1000 Kg/ha, 1000-2500 Kg/ha & more than 2500 Kg/ha, respectively.

Districts were placed in different categories depending upon the area and productivity levels and three categories were considered viz., High area-Medium productivity (HM),

Medium area - High productivity (MH), Medium area-Medium productivity (MM) and Low area - Medium productivity (LM). The districts with HM category were found to be five in number (Hamirpur, Kangra, Mandi, Shimla and Una) (Fig 2.3). There were three districts each in MM (Bilaspur, Sirmaur and Solan) and LM (Chamba, Kinnaur and Lahaul-spiti) category. The sole district Kullu represent MH category. This analysis indicates that there exists a scope for improvement of the productivity in these districts.

Fig 2.3 Potential area of wheat crop

2.8 Climate change and variability during growing season of wheat

Climate variability refers to the climatic parameter of a region varying from its long-term mean. Every year on a specific time period, the climate of a location is different. For example some years have below average rainfall, some have average or above average rainfall. We are not assured of getting the same amount of rainfall every year. The actual rainfall varying from the mean presents drought and flood conditions. However, climate change is a change in the statistical distribution of weather patterns when that change lasts for an extended period of time at least few decades. India is becoming more vulnerable to climate change as extreme weather events are on rise and major portion of population derive their livelihoods from agriculture and allied sectors.

2.8.1 Role of minimum temperature during *rabi* season in the northern region of the country

Due to passage of western disturbances, the northern region of the country experiences wide range of temperature fluctuations during the *rabi* season. Minimum temperature is one of the parameters that had been identified as a key factor in determination of crop growth, yield variations and severity of pest/disease attack. Table 2.1 illustrates the variability character of maximum and minimum temperatures for Palampur (November 5 to May 20), Malan, Bajaura and Shimla (November 11 to May 29), during *rabi* season (200 days each) for four seasons (2011-12 to 2014-15). Similar analyses was also carried out in the Delhi region (IARI, New Delhi, 1992) for the *rabi* season October 8 to 31st March (175 days) in two seasons (1988-89 & 1989-90). The results indicated that CV values of minimum temperature were higher followed by mean and maximum temperature at all the stations studied.

Table 2.1 Coefficient of variation (%) in temperature at different locations during wheat growth period

Period (days)	Palampur				Malan				Bajaura				Shimla			
	Maximum temperature															
	2011-12	2012-13	2013-14	2014-15	2011-12	2012-13	2013-14	2014-15	2011-12	2012-13	2013-14	2014-15	2011-12	2012-13	2013-14	2014-15
01-20	4	5	6	4	4	20	3	3	5	12	6	7	10	12	8	6
21-40	10	18	7	9	8	6	8	27	13	24	9	38	13	24	13	33
41-60	6	12	11	15	26	7	6	9	23	17	25	19	35	16	26	14
61-80	27	15	17	21	11	13	8	15	23	28	22	19	37	26	20	33
81-100	13	15	15	16	11	11	11	12	23	32	35	29	23	32	37	16
101-120	17	23	24	21	11	12	9	18	22	25	22	22	13	25	23	29
121-140	16	10	16	18	13	9	14	13	14	21	23	23	19	18	18	18
141-160	7	14	12	16	12	6	5	18	16	10	14	19	14	8	11	19
161-180	7	9	15	10	6	10	6	6	12	10	13	6	9	12	9	8
181-200	6	20	8	9	2	12	3	7	17	17	16	13	7	13	9	9
Minimum temperature																
01-20	15	13	19	24	9	14	10	14	73	89	123	132	16	26	17	14
21-40	26	23	16	26	16	6	11	21	104	110	213	73	30	51	31	55
41-60	69	34	28	34	17	28	7	13	62	600	635	2351	81	69	66	35
61-80	62	65	44	32	16	18	14	14	68	1319	117	158	331	75	67	128
81-100	50	37	35	41	32	22	21	27	91	81	141	118	117	50	97	52
101-120	29	28	36	29	14	15	11	13	48	46	42	53	35	48	44	73
121-140	42	18	25	30	19	10	8	22	42	30	35	43	37	28	33	35
141-160	14	18	14	16	19	10	7	10	20	20	18	13	24	15	23	26
161-180	13	13	23	14	10	9	7	9	21	14	23	17	22	18	18	16
181-200	14	15	11	14	3	15	14	4	14	13	12	14	20	17	16	14

The coefficient of variation in minimum temperature for the entire season was found to be much higher (2-4 times) at these stations as compared to maximum temperature.

2.9 Stable rainfall period for wheat cultivation

In the present study the suitability of wheat crop varieties of different maturity durations at different stations viz., Bajaura, Malan, Palampur and Shimla was examined. For this, rainfall periods having weekly rainfall of 15 mm and 150 % coefficient of variation of

rainfall were considered as “stable” periods. The rainfall data of 29, 15, 41 and 30 years for respective stations were considered for this analysis.

From 8 January to May 6, a period of 119 days was identified as stable rainfall periods for Palampur (Fig 2.4). The stable rainfall period was found to be 84 days (8 Jan –1 April) at Malan and 112 days (8 Jan – 29 April) each at Bajaura & Shimla. The study revealed that for effective seedling emergence and crop establishment, sufficient soil moisture is conserved through effective soil moisture conservation technologies like plastic mulch, a good wheat crop can be raised even under rain fed conditions as rainfall probability is fairly high after January and later till soft dough stage which declines hence after. Similar analysis had also been attempted for crop planning in Solan district of Himachal Pradesh (Baweja, 2011).

Fig 2.4 Stable rainfall period for wheat cultivation at Palampur

Table 2.2 Stable rainfall period for wheat cultivation at different stations of Himachal Pradesh

Station	Data base (years)	Stable rainfall period (days)
Palampur	41	08 Jan- 06 May (119)
Bajaura	29	08 Jan- 29 April (112)
Malan	15	08 Jan- 01 April (84)
Shimla	30	08 Jan- 29 April (112)

Chapter 3

Crop weather relationship

A comprehensive knowledge on physiological processes in crop plants such as photosynthesis, transpiration, growth and development as influenced by the process of energy and mass exchange has led to the development of dynamic crop-growth models and these are increasingly applied to estimate crop yields at regional levels. At the same time, traditional empirical-statistical models continued to be developed to understand and quantify the role of weather variables in determining the crop productivity of a given location/region. Crop-weather relationship studies were started at Palampur Centre under All India Coordinated Research Project on Agrometeorology (AICRPAM) during 1999-2000 and continued till 2007-08 with three wheat varieties viz., HPW42, HS 240 & HPW 147 under rain fed condition. Since 2010-11, five varieties viz., VL 907, VL 804, VL 829, VL 892 & HS 490 were tested both under rain fed and irrigated conditions till 2014-15 at Palampur station. Data from the work carried out on wheat at this Centre and some data from All India Coordinated Wheat and Barley Improvement Project at other stations in the state was re-analysed and results are reported here-under:

3.1 Phenological stages and growing degree days

The role of temperature on phenology of five wheat varieties grown under rain fed and irrigated conditions were evaluated for four years (2010-11 to 2013-14) at Palampur. Perusal of data on number of days taken for completion of different phenological stages of rain fed and irrigated wheat indicate that days taken decreased with delay in sowing in all varieties (Table 3.1). The rain fed wheat completed its life cycle in more number of days as its emergence was delayed due to scarce soil moisture at the time of sowing. The difference in 5th November date was larger during tillering to grain filling phases. Though the total number of days taken to complete the life cycle were more by 1-6 days under rain fed condition, yet effective number of days taken to complete tillering to heading stage was reduced by 9-15 days in VL 907 & HS 490, 11-16 days in VL 829 & VL 892 and 9-19 days in VL 804 for all the sowing dates, difference being larger in early dates in sum of the varieties. The yield reduction in rain fed wheat can be explained in terms of number of days taken but the yield reduction continues to be drastic even in the later dates wherein the differences were narrow. Correspondingly, the rain fed wheat accumulated higher thermal time, growing degree days (GDD) and followed the pattern of number of days taken for completion of different phenophases (Table 3.2). Photo-thermal units (PTU) and

Heliothermal units (HTU) for both the conditions were also evaluated and presented in Annexure 3 & 3a.

Table 3.1 Days taken for completion of different phenophases in wheat crop under rain fed and irrigated conditions at Palampur

Varieties	Phenophases	Days taken to complete different phenophases							
		5 th November		20 th November		5 th December		20 th December	
		RF	IR	RF	IR	RF	IR	RF	IR
VL 907	Emergence	32	12	25	13	20	14	18	13
	Tillering	80	57	69	53	60	50	48	44
	Heading	141	133	130	127	119	123	114	117
	Grain filling	158	154	146	143	135	137	128	131
	Physiological maturity	188	183	176	173	162	162	148	151
VL 804	Emergence	34	12	23	15	21	13	17	13
	Tillering	80	54	68	54	59	48	49	44
	Heading	138	133	130	128	123	123	114	117
	Grain filling	158	153	145	144	136	138	128	129
	Physiological maturity	189	184	176	172	162	163	147	148
VL 829	Emergence	33	13	24	13	21	13	17	13
	Tillering	77	59	64	53	60	48	49	44
	Heading	138	136	128	130	120	123	112	119
	Grain filling	156	153	144	145	134	137	126	130
	Physiological maturity	188	183	175	174	161	160	148	150
VL 892	Emergence	34	13	24	13	20	13	18	13
	Tillering	80	60	69	55	60	49	50	44
	Heading	139	133	128	126	118	121	110	117
	Grain filling	155	153	144	142	134	135	124	133
	Physiological maturity	187	182	176	172	161	160	147	148
HS 490	Emergence	34	13	23	15	19	14	17	11
	Tillering	80	58	68	56	59	48	47	38
	Heading	141	131	129	127	119	121	112	116
	Grain filling	158	152	145	142	133	136	126	130
	Physiological maturity	188	182	176	171	162	159	146	146

*IR: Irrigated; RF: Rain fed

3.2 Models to predict Phenophases

Regression equations were developed using the relation between GDD and number of days taken for completion of different phenophases of different varieties grown under rain fed and irrigated conditions for the period of four years, 2010-11 to 2013-14. The equations were tested with the independent data sets of 2014-15. The results obtained are presented in Table 3.3. It was found that up to 5th December, during grain filling the difference in observed and predicted values varied between 1-9 days both under irrigated as well as rain fed wheat. The values were however mostly overestimated in irrigated whereas underestimated in rain fed conditions.

Table 3.2 Phenophase- wise accumulated growing degree days taken by different wheat varieties sown on different dates under rain fed and irrigated conditions

Phenophases	Accumulated growing degree days (^o C days)							
	5 th November		20 th November		5 th December		20 th December	
	RF	IRR	RF	IRR	RF	IRR	RF	IRR
VL 907								
Emergence	316	136	219	119	146	111	80	68
Tillering	609	498	467	390	361	299	191	172
Heading	1104	1021	996	961	912	957	660	717
Grain filling	1329	1288	1203	1169	1118	1154	831	878
Phy. maturity	1818	1743	1713	1665	1595	1593	1155	1214
VL 804								
Emergence	334	138	208	143	155	106	84	63
Tillering	610	482	458	388	355	292	202	169
Heading	1069	1016	1002	977	959	960	667	728
Grain filling	1328	1264	1190	1185	1135	1164	838	846
Phy. maturity	1836	1755	1708	1639	1598	1605	1144	1138
VL 829								
Emergence	320	143	217	120	154	103	112	55
Tillering	595	512	437	386	360	290	318	173
Heading	1065	1078	975	1008	923	958	738	796
Grain filling	1306	1274	1182	1198	1108	1161	964	932
Phy. maturity	1820	1735	1700	1668	1566	1561	1391	1345
VL 892								
Emergence	328	144	202	132	149	100	84	68
Tillering	612	515	466	396	354	292	202	170
Heading	1079	1026	959	973	890	945	631	735
Grain filling	1293	1262	1179	1199	1111	1133	790	929
Phy. maturity	1813	1715	1704	1644	1583	1551	1154	1147
HS 490								
Emergence	327	148	209	139	138	111	79	54
Tillering	612	503	459	395	349	290	194	138
Heading	1106	995	988	966	904	932	648	718
Grain filling	1329	1250	1190	1152	1096	1150	804	880
Phy. maturity	1818	1719	1717	1625	1590	1546	1135	1126
Pooled								
Emergence	325	142	211	131	148	106	88	62
Tillering	607	502	457	391	356	293	221	164
Heading	1085	1027	984	977	918	950	669	739
Grain filling	1317	1268	1189	1181	1113	1153	845	893
Phy. maturity	1821	1734	1709	1648	1587	1571	1196	1194

RF- Rain fed; IRR- Irrigated; Phy. Maturity- Physiological maturity

The differences between observed and predicted days for completion of grain-filling appear to be the least. In the majority of the cases, the model under- estimated under rain fed and over-estimated under irrigated condition. Under 20th December date the model under-estimated under both the conditions and the differences were much larger. A similar observation but with different varieties (HPW 42, HPW 147 and HS 240) also indicates that GDD is the best index to predict 50 per cent grain filling (Prasad *et al.*, 2005).

Table 3.3 Difference between observed and predicted days taken for completion of different phenophases of wheat

Varieties	Phenophases	Difference between observed and predicted days							
		5 th November		20 th November		5 th December		20 th December	
		RF	IRR	RF	IRR	RF	IRR	RF	IRR
VL 907	Emergence	16	-6	10	2	4	3	-2	-4
	Tillering	14	13	22	14	19	3	-11	-17
	Heading	3	20	-1	7	1	15	-21	-14
	Grain filling	-7	8	-6	2	-2	-1	-21	-17
	Physiological maturity	-9	-14	-7	-11	-7	-10	-28	-25
VL 804	Emergence	20	1	9	4	5	1	-1	-5
	Tillering	14	11	19	14	20	1	-8	-16
	Heading	0	21	-2	10	8	8	-20	-12
	Grain filling	-8	7	-7	1	-1	-1	-22	-21
	Physiological maturity	-6	-14	-6	-12	-7	-9	-27	-31
VL 829	Emergence	16	2	12	2	6	2	4	-5
	Tillering	10	18	15	15	19	2	14	-14
	Heading	0	29	-4	8	5	15	-16	-7
	Grain filling	-8	9	-7	2	-3	1	-10	-12
	Physiological maturity	-8	-13	-6	-9	-9	-11	-14	-18
VL 892	Emergence	18	2	11	3	5	3	-1	-3
	Tillering	13	16	22	16	18	2	-7	-15
	Heading	4	26	-3	10	0	13	-22	-11
	Grain filling	-9	9	-7	3	-2	-2	-24	-13
	Physiological maturity	-9	-15	-7	-12	-8	-12	-28	-30
HS 490	Emergence	19	3	8	5	1	4	-1	-5
	Tillering	14	16	19	16	17	4	-11	-20
	Heading	1	21	-11	11	0	6	-21	-14
	Grain filling	-7	6	-8	-3	-4	-3	-25	-18
	Physiological maturity	-8	-15	-6	-12	-8	-12	-28	-30

IR: Irrigated; RF: Rain fed

3.3 Productivity of wheat as influenced by temperature during reproductive phase

The influence of temperature on crop phenology and productivity of five wheat cultivars (VL- 907, VL 804, VL- 829, VL 892, and HS-490) was studied from a five year experiment (2010-11 to 2014-15) conducted under rain fed condition which revealed that maximum wheat yields can be realized during the years with mean temperature during reproductive phase prevailing in the range of 17.2 °C in variety VL-804 and 18.2 °C in variety HS-490 (Fig 3.1). An increase in the temperature to 19.3 & 19.7 °C above this optimum value during reproductive phase resulted in drastic reduction in grain yield which were in the range of 82.9 to 84.1 per cent compared to yields that were realized at mean temperature of 17.2 and 18.2°C, in both varieties, respectively. Similar yield reduction was also noticed in remaining three varieties under rain fed condition with increase in temperature.

Fig 3.2 Mean temperature vs yield during reproductive phase under rain fed condition in variety VL 804 (a) & HS 490 (b) and under irrigated condition in VL 804 (c) & HS 490 (d)

Under irrigated condition, maximum yields were realized during the years with mean temperature during reproductive phase prevailing in the range of 19.6 °C in variety HS-490 and 19.7 °C in variety VL-804 (Fig 3.2). An increase in the temperature to 22.0 and 22.3 °C above this optimum value during reproductive phase resulted in drastic reduction in grain yield which were in the range of 72.5 to 76.4 per cent compared to yields that were realized at mean temperature of 19.6 and 19.7 °C, in both varieties, respectively. Similar yield reduction was also noticed in remaining three varieties under irrigated condition.

The study further suggests that with raising temperatures, the yield reduction was much higher under rain fed condition than irrigated condition. All the five varieties could not only withstand higher temperatures but also can perform better under irrigated conditions.

3.4 Performance of wheat under varied thermal environments

To understand the performance of wheat in respect of number of tillers, days taken for heading and yield of all the five varieties, the sum of departures of daily temperatures from normal for each fortnight of different months (November to April) of the wheat growing season were calculated over last five years (Table 3.4).

From the table, it was observed that wheat growing season during 2013-14 was the warmer (+126.5 °C) followed by wheat growing season in year 2014-15 (+29.7 °C). The *rabi* 2010-11 has experienced coolest wheat season with cumulative temperature deviation of -81.3 °C followed by 2012-13 (-59.7 °C) and 2011-12 (-54.1 °C).

Table 3.4 Sum of the deviation of temperature from normal for different fortnights of wheat growing season at Palampur

Season/ particulars	Sum of deviations of temperature from normal (°C)												Over the season
	November		December		January		February		March		April		
	I	II	I	II	I	II	I	II	I	II	I	II	
2010-11	-13.7	-19.9	+1.05	-10.5	-4.3	+16.0	-40.0	+23.1	-3.55	-54.2	+11.9	+12.3	-81.3
2011-12	-17.0	-22.2	-25.1	-12.1	+11.3	+28.1	+20.4	-6.6	+9.8	-45.6	-26.8	+31.7	-54.1
2012-13	+6.4	+7.4	-13.4	-19.9	+0.3	-1.75	-13.7	+10.1	-34.8	-9.8	-10.9	+20.5	-59.7
2013-14	+32.7	-1.7	-7.5	+11.5	+4.75	-13.3	+14.4	+14.2	+31.3	-3.3	+15.7	+27.8	+126.5
2014-15	+5.3	-1.05	-4.05	+10.3	-9.5	+14.2	-5.1	-25.3	+28.3	-19.8	+32.2	+4.1	+29.7

Our studies on simulation modelling presented in next section indicate that warming during January, February and first fortnight of March have beneficial effect on wheat yield under mid hill conditions of Himachal Pradesh. In the present investigation it can be seen that during second fortnight of January and February (2010-11) and during February and first fortnight of March (2013-14) the temperature increased which increased the yield considerably.

3.5 Effect of temperature on tillering, days to heading and grain yield

Tillering in wheat growing season with above normal (2014-15) temperature deviations showed that number of tillers per meter row length were lowest 143 in warm growing environment of very late sown conditions compared to normal sown cooler growing environment of 2010-11 & 2012-13 (Table 3.5). Days taken for heading reduced during 2014-15 with warmer growing season (147 days in normal sowing conditions) compared to 2010-11 with cooler growing season (161 days). Comparison of grain yield of wheat during the year with higher temperatures to the year with below normal temperature indicates that the wheat yield under both normal and very late sown conditions was higher in cooler years.

Table 3.5 Effect of fluctuating seasonal temperature on tillering in wheat crops different varieties

Sowing environment	Tiller/m ²			Heading (DAS)			Grain yield		
	2010-11	2012-13	2014-15	2010-11	2012-13	2014-15	2010-11	2012-13	2014-15
Normal sown*	254	190	162	161	150	147	4461	3015	2132
Very late sown#	251	184	143	129	133	128	3469	2759	1633
Thermal conditions	-81.3	-59.7	+29.7	-81.3	-59.7	+29.7	-81.3	-59.7	+29.7

*Normal sown- Nov. 4-11, #Very late sown-December 5-20

3.6 Pheno-thermal Index

Pheno-thermal Index (ratio between accumulated GDD to the number of days during a particular phase) during different phases of crop growth were worked out for four years (2010-11 to 2013-14) and are shown in Table 3.6

The pheno-thermal Index (PTI) values ranged from 5.5 to 17.4. The two salient features were (i) within a phase the index showed little variation (ii) Among the phases, the highest value was recorded during grain filling to physiological maturity, followed by heading to grain filling, entire growth phase, tillering to heading, sowing to emergence and emergence to tillering. Taking entire crop period into consideration, the PTI was found to be nearly constant around a value of 10 degrees/day which was lower to that reported under Delhi conditions (Chakravarty and Sastry, 1983).

Table 3.6 Pheno-thermal index in different varieties of wheat during

Phenophase	Photo thermal index (degree days)									
	VL 907		VL 804		VL 829		VL 892		HS490	
	RF	IR	RF	IR	RF	RF	IR	RF	IR	RF
S-E	8.1	8.7	8.0	8.9	8.1	8.7	8.1	8.7	8.1	8.7
E-T	5.6	6.2	5.5	6.3	5.5	6.2	5.5	6.1	5.6	6.1
T-H	9.1	8.4	9.2	8.3	8.9	8.6	9.1	8.4	9.2	8.2
H-G	13.8	13.7	13.8	13.7	13.5	13.4	13.6	13.7	14.3	13.8
G-P	17.4	17.3	17.3	17.1	17.2	17.1	17.1	17.0	17.4	16.7
Entire growth phase	9.8	9.8	9.8	9.7	9.8	9.8	9.8	9.7	10.0	9.6

S-E: Sowing to emergence, E-T: Emergence to tillering, T-H: Tillering to heading, H-G: Heading to Grain filling, G-P: Grain filling to Physiological maturity, IR: Irrigated, RF: Rain fed

3.7 Natural resource use efficiency of wheat

Natural resource use by different wheat varieties for rain fed and irrigated conditions was quantified in terms of Heat Use Efficiency (HUE), Radiation Use Efficiency (RUE) and Water Use Efficiency (WUE) facilitating identification of varieties suitable for the late and advanced sowing environments. This was accomplished through staggered sowing of five wheat cultivars (VL- 907, VL 804, VL- 829, VL 892, and HS-490) for a period of four years (2010-11 to 2013-14). It can be inferred from present investigation that differential response

exists for HUE, RUE and WUE. These efficiencies were higher under late sown rain fed conditions compared to early rain fed conditions (Table 3.7). Barring few exceptions, the efficiency to use these resources generally decreased with delay in sowing under irrigated conditions. Variety HS-490 was found to be more efficient than the other varieties studied when sown on or later than 20th November. The study also suggests that the resource utilization efficiencies were much higher under irrigated condition than rain fed condition.

Table 3.7 Resource utilization efficiencies of wheat varieties sown on different dates under rain fed and irrigated conditions at Palampur

Varieties/ date of sowing	D ₁ - 5 November			D ₂ - 20 November			D ₃ - 5 December			D ₁ - 20 December		
	HUE (kg/ha/ ° days)	RUE (kg/ha/ /MJ)	WUE (kg/ha/ mm)	HUE (kg/ha/ ° days)	RUE (kg/ha/ MJ)	WUE (kg/ha/ mm)	HUE (kg/ha/ ° days)	RUE (kg/ha/ MJ)	WUE (kg/ha/ mm)	HUE (kg/ha/ ° days)	RUE (kg/ha/ MJ)	WUE (kg/ha/ mm)
Rain fed												
VL-907	1.1	0.7	5.3	1.4	0.9	6.5	1.9	1.2	8.7	1.7	1.0	7.0
VL-804	1.3	0.8	5.8	1.4	0.9	6.6	1.5	1.0	6.9	1.7	1.1	7.2
VL-829	1.4	0.9	6.8	1.3	0.8	5.8	1.8	1.1	7.7	1.8	1.1	7.6
VL-892	1.4	0.9	7.2	1.3	0.8	6.2	1.8	1.1	8.0	1.7	1.0	6.8
HS-490	1.1	0.7	5.2	1.3	0.9	6.4	1.8	1.2	8.1	2.1	1.3	8.9
Irrigated												
VL-907	2.4	1.5	11.0	2.0	1.3	9.3	2.1	1.3	9.5	1.8	1.1	7.8
VL-804	2.4	1.5	10.9	2.0	1.2	8.9	2.0	1.3	9.1	2.0	1.3	8.6
VL-829	2.0	1.3	9.1	1.8	1.2	8.3	1.7	1.1	7.4	1.9	1.2	8.2
VL-892	1.6	1.0	7.9	2.0	1.2	8.8	2.0	1.3	8.8	2.1	1.3	8.8
HS-490	2.4	1.5	10.8	2.6	1.6	11.3	2.4	1.5	10.2	2.2	1.4	9.4

The *aestivum* varieties of wheat, the efficiencies at Udaipur, Raipur and Solapur stations were found to be higher than what were observed at Palampur (adapted from various annual reports of AICRPAM). This indicates lower efficiencies achieved in Himachal Pradesh, warrant drastic improvement in crop management strategies.

3.8 Relationship between wheat yield and weather parameters

Optimum temperature limits to produced wheat yields ≥ 3.5 t/ha were identified from eleven years of experimentation (1999-2000 to 2009-10) under rain fed condition. Maximum temperature in the range of 17.8 to 19.9 °C (optimum 18.6 °C) and minimum temperature in the range of 5.2 to 8.0 °C (optimum 6.7 °C) during vegetative and maximum in the range of 20.6 to 27.1 °C (optimum 23.4 °C) and minimum in the range of 8.2 to 13.3 °C (optimum 10.9 °C) during reproductive phase were found to be optimum to realize higher yields (Table 3.8). Further rise in temperature during vegetative and reproductive phases reduces the yield to 2-3 t/ha due to reduced soil moisture. It was also found that warming during vegetative

phase had the capacity to further decrease the yield to ≤ 2 t/ha. This hypothesis was tested utilizing the *rabi* 2010-11 yield data which showed that the validity of the hypothesis is reasonably high. The above results were also reported in the AICRPAM Annual Progress Report (2010-11).

Table 3.8 Optimum temperature for different phenophases in rain fed wheat at Palampur

Temperatures	Vegetative phases	Reproductive phase	Maturity phase
Yield (≥ 3t/ha)			
Maximum ($^{\circ}$ C) 2010-11	17.8 - 19.9*(18.6) 16.5-18.2 (17.4)	20.6 -27.1 (23.4) 19.8-24.0 (22.5)	27.7 – 31.2 (29.2) 26.3-27.4 (26.4)
Minimum ($^{\circ}$ C) 2010-11	5.2 – 8.0 (6.7) 5.1-6.9 (5.7)	8.2 – 13.3 (10.9) 8.9-11.1 (10.3)	15.4 – 18.3 (16.4) 14.4-15.6 (15.0)
Yield (2-3 t/ha)			
Maximum ($^{\circ}$ C)	17.2 – 22.1 (18.9)	22.2-29.2 (25.9)	27.9 – 32.3 (30.1)
Minimum ($^{\circ}$ C)	5.3 – 10.1 (7.5)	10.1 – 16.8 (13.8)	15.6 – 19.7 (18.1)
Yield (≤ 2t/ha)			
Maximum ($^{\circ}$ C)	19.8-20.2 (20.0)	21.0-22.2 (21.7)	27.9 – 28.7 (28.4)
Minimum ($^{\circ}$ C)	7.4-7.9 (7.7)	10.2 – 10.5(10.3)	14.9 – 15.4 (15.2)

*Threshold temperature limits identified

The similar but higher optimum temperatures values have been reported for other stations (adapted from various reports of AICRPAM) which indicate that the wheat crop has a capacity to with stand higher temperature and can perform still better under irrigated conditions.

3.9 Response of wheat to hydrothermal environment

Wheat data from the reports of All India Coordinated Wheat and Barley Improvement Research Project for four years i.e., 2011-12, 2012-13, 2013-14 & 2014-15 for timely sown variety, VL-804 having 150 to 180 days duration grown under normal and late conditions were analyzed and presented in Table 3.9.

This variety sown under normal dates of sowing (4-11 November) completed life cycle around 190-210 days. It used around 1900-3300 heat units and produced around 23-48q/ha when around 450-500 mm rainfall was received. Same variety when sown under late conditions (25 November-01 December) completed life cycle 165-190 days, due to variable thermal regimes in different regions. It used around 1900-3000 heat units and produced around 19-50 q/ha under same rainfall regime. The yield reduction due to late sowing though was only 5.6% at Palampur but the reduction varied between 20.7 and 28.1percent at Malan and Shimla stations, respectively. This variety produced 49 q/ha at Bajaura station and

utilized around 1900 heat units in 190 days. This thermal condition seems to be ideal for this variety. The other conditions encountered at different stations are given in Table 3.10

Table 3.9 Days to maturity, heat units, total rainfall (mm) and yield (q/ha) of wheat at different stations in different sowing windows

Date of sowing / station	Normal sowing				Late sowing				Yield reduction (%) over normal sowing
	(4-11 November)				(25 November- 1 December)				
	Days	Heat Unit	ARF	Yield	Days	Heat Unit	ARF	Yield	
Bajaura	206	2533	480	48.2	192	1890	485	49.0	+1.7
Malan	194	3068	509	44.9	177	3046	506	35.6	-20.7
Shimla	215	1901	466	27.0	193	2143	430	19.4	-28.1
Palampur	191	3341	516	23.3	166	3049	514	22.0	-5.6

3.10 Response of nitrogen under rain fed conditions

The data of experiments to study the response of nitrogen under rain fed conditions was taken three stations viz., Shimla, Bajaura and Malan and four wheat varieties viz., VL 804, VL 907, HS 507 and HPW 349 raised under 40, 60 and 80 kg/ha nitrogen keeping phosphorus and potash as recommended dose for the period of four years i.e., 2011-12, 2012-13, 2013-14 & 2014-15 from the reports of All India Coordinated Wheat and Barley Improvement Research Project.

Higher dosages of N were found to be beneficial but having differential response across the locations under irrigated condition as the yield increased from 22.8 to 27.2 q/ha at Shimla, 34.9 to 47.1 q/ha at Bajaura and 25.3 to 30.1 q/ha at Malan by increasing the nitrogen from 40 kg/ha to 80 kg/ha .

Rainfall however seems to play an important role which is conspicuous at Shimla wherein due to lower rainfall (332.1 mm) during 2011-12, crop could not take benefit of higher dose of nitrogen and yield was reduced from 18.3 (60 kg N) to 16.2 q/ha (80 kg N) (Table 3.11). It can be seen that during 2013-14 and 2014-15 the increase in yield due to higher rainfall was not in same proportion as in case of 2012-13. In general, 400-500 mm rainfall is proved more beneficial for the crop at these stations to take the maximum benefit from the nitrogen applied. The rain fall above and below this range had negative effect on the wheat yield even under application of higher doses of N. Rainfall around 30 mm during October to December, 400 mm during January to March and 75 mm during April to May were found to be more beneficial having additive effect on the yield. These rainfall amounts were therefore helpful to take full advantage of the fertilizers applied.

Table 3.10 Available soil moisture, potential evapo-transpiration and water surplus for soils of 150 mm water holding capacity in different stations of Himachal Pradesh

Week	Palampur			Bajaura			Malan			Shimla		
	ASM	PET	WS	ASM	PET	WS	ASM	PET	WS	ASM	PET	WS
40	123.6	20.8	3.3	75.8	24.8	0.0	117.4	21.3	4.5	115.7	17.3	2.2
41	114.9	19.7	4.7	69.3	21.9	0.2	106.5	20.3	2.8	109.0	15.8	4.1
42	106.2	18.3	1.2	67.9	19.7	3.7	95.7	19.4	0.0	103.8	14.6	2.4
43	97.2	16.7	0.0	62.4	17.9	0.0	88.4	17.7	0.0	96.0	13.3	0.7
44	89.6	15.5	0.5	56.6	16.3	0.0	79.6	16.9	0.0	89.2	12.1	0.2
45*	84.6	14.1	0.0	56.9	14.1	0.0	74.9	15.8	0.0	84.3	11.1	0.0
46	80.7	13.1	0.0	54.5	12.8	0.0	75.3	13.9	0.3	79.6	10.1	0.0
47	76.2	12.1	0.0	52.7	10.7	0.3	69.9	12.6	0.0	78.7	9.2	0.0
48**	75.6	11.0	0.2	54.0	9.3	1.2	65.1	11.9	0.0	75.1	8.7	0.6
49	73.0	10.7	0.5	53.8	8.2	0.4	61.7	11.5	0.0	72.8	8.2	0.5
50	77.7	9.7	1.6	55.4	6.8	3.1	65.4	10.3	3.8	72.7	7.3	3.2
51	80.1	9.6	0.9	61.6	6.5	0.9	63.2	10.5	0.0	75.4	7.2	0.0
52	88.8	10.4	3.2	67.2	7.0	1.1	61.8	12.0	0.0	79.7	7.8	1.2
1	94.6	8.8	6.5	73.0	3.4	3.2	66.7	9.5	0.0	81.6	6.5	2.7
2	101.7	9.1	5.9	81.6	4.1	1.2	69.9	9.6	7.9	89.1	6.6	0.6
3	108.4	9.2	5.6	98.3	4.6	1.7	83.4	9.7	3.7	102.5	6.8	2.7
4	117.6	9.9	13.2	103.3	6.3	0.5	91.2	10.5	0.3	108.1	7.9	2.4
5	115.7	10.8	9.3	103.6	6.7	4.5	93.5	11.9	4.1	107.3	8.6	2.8
6	120.5	11.5	11.2	118.8	7.9	8.6	103.0	12.2	9.3	116.0	9.0	8.3
7	124.0	12.5	20.5	127.4	8.7	14.2	106.8	13.2	7.3	121.3	9.5	6.5

ASM: Available soil moisture (mm), PET: Potential Evapo-transpiration (mm), WS: Water surplus (mm) *Normal sowing (04-11 Nov), ** Late sowing (25 Nov-01 Dec)

In a case study to know the effect of rainfall and sowing dates on wheat production conducted by Prasad *et al.*, 1995 indicate that the probabilities of getting a dry week, a fortnight after the *rabi* sowing was fairly high. Chances of getting at least 10 mm weekly rainfall builds up only after meteorological week 49 (3-9th December). This amount is sufficient for proper germination of winter-season crops. Therefore, in the event of prolonged dry spell after the withdrawal of monsoon the sowing of wheat should be ensured by the week 50 (10-16th December). Further, the experience of working with rain fed wheat also indicates that rainfall of December and January is beneficial for the early and timely sown wheat whereas January rainfall is beneficial for late sown wheat.

Table 3.11 Effect of nitrogen and rainfall on wheat yield under rain fed conditions

Years	Shimla				Bajaura				Malan								
	Rainfall (mm)		N1	N2	N3	Rainfall (mm)		N1	N2	N3	Rainfall (mm)		N1	N2	N3		
2011-12	Oct-Dec	36.0	17.0	18.3	16.2	Oct-Dec	34.4	30.5	37.7	40.4	Oct-Dec	25.4	21.8	25.5	28.2		
	Jan-March	201.8				Jan-March	240.7				Jan-March	273.5					
	April-May	94.3				April-May	99.2				April-May	47.9					
	Total	332.1				Total	374.3				Total	346.8					
2012-13	Oct-Dec	29.3	30.9	33.1	39.0	Oct-Dec	14.0	38.8	44.7	51.0	Oct-Dec	66.8	23.5	25.6	26.5		
	Jan-March	415.3				Jan-March	324.7				Jan-March	183.7					
	April-May	38.1				April-May	75.0				April-May	44.5					
	Total	482.7				Total	413.7				Total	295.0					
2013-14	Oct-Dec	93.4	21.5	26.0	25.1	Oct-Dec	28.4	35.4	42.3	48.7	Oct-Dec	129.3	28.5	30.1	33.4		
	Jan-March	281.8				Jan-March	349.3				Jan-March	339.8					
	April-May	150.5				April-May	203.2				April-May	74.4					
	Total	525.7				Total	580.9				Total	543.5					
2014-15	Oct-Dec	126.9	21.9	25.7	28.7	Oct-Dec	88.7	35.0	42.9	48.3	Oct-Dec	99.1	27.2	30.0	32.5		
	Jan-March	374.6				Jan-March	356.6				Jan-March	772.7					
	April-May	32.6				April-May	258.7				April-May	105.9					
	Total	534.1				Total	704.0				Total	977.7					
Mean yield			22.8	25.8	27.2	Mean yield			34.9	41.9	47.1	Mean yield			25.3	27.8	30.1

N1, N2 & N3-Yield kg/ha when nitrogen applied @ 40, 60 & 80 kg/ha, respectively

3.11 Weather effects on yellow rust of wheat

Yellow rust also called as stripe rust in wheat is caused by *Puccinia striiformis* Westend. Meteorological factors influence the host and rust differently. The rust mycelium can be present in seed but it never passes from the seed coat to the newly emerging seedling, unless favourable weather prevails. Away from the living host, rust may persist up to several days as uredospores and up to several years as teleutospores. Reinfection and multiplication depend on susceptible host and favourable weather. Yellow rust is available on the host plant grasses growing in hilly tracts. Optimum temperature for rapid multiplication is mean temperatures between 9 to 13 °C, with relative humidity greater than 70 per cent and partly cloudy conditions for a week's period. Wind force spreads the rust to distance places. A long warm autumn and short mild winter are favourable environments (Bishnoi, 1988). A few grasses may act as necessary hosts, high sporulation temperatures (20 to 25 °C) stimulates the rate of germination, very low temperatures (2°C) also stimulate the germination rate of some

rices. High sporulation temperatures induce a lower optimum temperature for subsequent germination of the spores produced. These facts may explain the adaptation of the rust to low winter and high summer temperatures. High relative humidity (>95%) also favours germination, especially with high sporulation temperatures (20°C) combined with supra-optimal germination temperatures ($\geq 15^\circ\text{C}$) (WMO 1969).

All improved wheat varieties at the time of release are resistant to the rust types prevalent for the zone to which recommendations are made. Later in due course of time these may become susceptible to the new races of these rusts, which also undergo changes by various mechanisms. It is therefore very important to grow the latest released varieties and discard the older type.

3. 11.1 Weather relations of yellow rust of wheat in Himachal Pradesh

The yellow rust starts appearing during first fortnight of January in the state and continues to appear till March. Literature indicates that the temperature range between 10-25 °C and relative humidity above 70% (i.e., cooler and wetter condition) from mid January onwards are favorable for incidence and further acceleration of this disease. During *rabi* 2014-15, the major wheat growing districts of the state viz., Bilaspur, Hamirpur, Una, Sirmaur and Kangra witnessed lower temperatures in February and March along with higher rainfall at most of the locations. The weather was largely favorable for the incidence of this disease and but it was found to be of low intensity in these districts. Spray of Tilt 20EC Propiconazole 25EC @ (0.2%) is recommended for application at the first appearance of this disease and repeated at 15 days interval if the disease remained above threshold level.

As per the reports of Department of Agriculture and Government of Himachal Pradesh, the yellow rust was monitored during January- February in the different parts of the state. Yellow rust was reported from some villages of district Bilaspur, Hamirpur, Kangra, Mandi, Sirmaur and Una which was found in traces during 1st fortnight of February.

To assess the weather relation of yellow rust, days with $\geq 10^\circ\text{C}$ and $\leq 20^\circ\text{C}$ maximum temperature, total rainfall and rainy days as an index of humidity during the month of February for five seasons viz., 2010-11, 2011-12, 2012-13, 2013-14 and 2014-15 was undertaken. Out of five seasons, two (2010-11 and 2011-12) were having high yellow rust whereas remaining three had low yellow rust severity. The average weather parameters of both the situations were compared and presented in Table 3.12. The rainfall below 100 mm during February with lesser number of rainy days was found to be favorable for the yellow rust incidence and spread. The higher number of days with maximum temperature between

10-20 °C favoured yellow rust in different regions over the years. This observation provides sufficient evidence in favour of our earlier finding which indicated that the more number of days with maximum temperatures between 10-20 °C are favorable for rust incidence and its spread.

Table 3.12 Number of days with mean and maximum temperature between 10 to 20 °C, rainfall and rainy days during February

Stations/ particulars	Days with 10-20 °C max. temperature		Rainfall (mm)		Rainy days	
	Yellow rust incidence					
	High	Low	High	Low	High	Low
Bajaura	21	18	87.0	169.6	13	13
Malan	21	19	61.5	281.7	7	9
Kangra	19	11	53.8	100.4	6	8
Akrot	13	11	55.4	100.2	4	8
Mean	17	15	60.0	128.0	7	9

Chapter 4

Calibration and validation of crop simulation models for wheat

The effect of various temperature regimes on wheat was studied using DSSAT v 4.5 model. The CERES-Wheat model, available in the DSSAT software package, is a wheat growth simulation model that was originally developed under the USDA-ARS Wheat Yield Project and the U.S. government multiagency AGRISTARS program (Ritchie and Otter 1985). It simulates the growth and development of wheat using daily time steps. While, simulating the growth it takes into account the effects of weather, genotype, soil, planting time, irrigations, fertilizer management, organic amendments, tillage and chemical applications. It also requires crop management information on planting date, planting depth, planting density, row spacing, time and amount of irrigation, fertilizer and organic amendments application etc. (Ritchie *et al.* 1998). The model is based on physiological processes that describe the responses of wheat to soil and other environmental conditions.

The meteorological data required for calculation of long term averages (normal) of weather parameters (sunshine, rainfall, maximum and minimum temperature) was used from the recorded values at Agromet observatory situated at Agronomy Farm, CSK HPKV, Palampur. The crop data required for calibration and validation of the model was obtained from the field trials conducted at the same location. The model was calibrated for the most popular wheat variety VL 829 grown in the region. This variety is grown in low and mid hill conditions of Himachal Pradesh under early sown rain fed conditions. The variety is tolerant to yellow and brown rust and loose smut having yield potential of 30-32 kg/ha. The rate of fertilizer application, irrigation and other management practices used in the model were as recommended by university while conducting the study. After the validation of the CERES-wheat model available in DSSAT v 4.5.0.0 was used as a research tool to study the effect of heat stress on wheat productivity. Three dates of sowing (early, November 5, normal November 20 and late December 5) with a difference of 15 days were selected to determine the date that remains less affected by heat stress. Heat stress scenarios were created in the model by using environment modification option available in the model. Both maximum and minimum temperatures were increased from normal in the increments of 0.5°C and were finally raised up to 3.0°C above long term average. The increase in temperature was imposed at fortnightly intervals starting from 1-15th December till 30th April, keeping the temperature normal during rest of the crop growth period. The model output in terms of wheat yield was used to calculate per cent deviation in wheat productivity from the respective time of sowing

under different heat stress scenarios. The other interventions taken for the study were: 1) 25% additional nitrogen of recommended dose and 2) The additional 6th irrigation in early, timely and late sowings. In order to assess the impact of the intervention, the all treatments were tested individually and in combination.

4.1 Effect of temperature variation on productivity of wheat

The perusal of the data showed that the model was calibrated well and phenological events match quite well (Table 4.1). The data shows that the difference between observed and simulated days taken for anthesis is -5 days and maturity +3 days. The r^2 value also varied between 0.84 to 1.0 and d-Stat 0.91 to 0.98 i.e., well within acceptable levels. The NRMSE values for days taken for anthesis and maturity, were in excellent range (<10%) as proposed by Jamieson *et al.* (1991).

The grain yield was also simulated quite well and the difference between observed and simulated was -164 kg/ha. The values of r^2 were however quite low, 0.28. The value of RMSE was acceptable 548.73 kg/ha. The d-Stat value was also 0.65 which was within acceptable levels.

Table 4.1. Validation of DSSAT v4.5

Variable Name	Mean		Std Dev		r-Square	Mean Diff.	Mean Abs. Diff.	RMSE	d-Stat	Used Obs
	Obs	Sim	Obs	Sim						
Anthesis days	130	124	14.24	11.97	0.84	-5	7	7.79	0.91	4
Grain yield kg/ha	3284	3086	586.03	421.94	0.28	-198	501	548.73	0.65	4
Maturity days	148	151	12.09	11.30	1.00	3	3	2.96	0.98	4

This analysis indicates that the model is working reasonably well and it should be possible to answer some of the important questions related to climate change, its impact and possible adaption/ management in wheat crop.

4.1.1 Effect of fortnightly rise in temperature during the season

The temperature was increased during different 15 days intervals starting from 1st December up to 30th April. The results of fortnightly temperature rise are presented in Fig 4.1. The temperature (both maximum and minimum) was increased from normal in increments of 0.5°C and was increased stepwise up to 3.0°C. The increase in temperature will benefit the timely sown wheat crop, especially if it occurs during February or first fortnight of March and it would be harmful if it occurs during 1-15th April. In case of late sown wheat it

will be beneficial if it increases during 2nd fortnight of January or 1-31st March. The increase in temperature would be harmful if it occurs during 1-15th March in case of early sown wheat. Temperature rise up to 0.5 °C will be more beneficial to timely and late sown wheat compared to early sown crop.

The increase in temperature by 1.0°C will be harmful if it occurs during 16-31st March in case of both early and timely sown wheat and 1-15th April in case of late sown wheat. The increase would be beneficial for timely sown wheat if it occurs either during 2nd fortnight of January or first fortnight of February.

The increase in temperature by 1.5°C will be harmful if it occurs during 16-31st March in case of both early and timely sown wheat and 1-15th April in case of late sown wheat. The increase would be beneficial for timely and late sown wheat if it occurs during 1st fortnight of January or first fortnight of March. It will also be beneficial for timely and late sown crop if it increases during 1-14th February and 15 to 28th February, respectively. The late sown wheat would be benefited more by 1.5°C increase in temperature during 15th February to 15th March.

The fortnightly increase in temperature by 2.0°C above normal will be harmful if it occurs during 16-31st March in early, timely and late sown wheat, the effect however, decreased with delay in sowing. The reduction would be encountered in late sown wheat, if this rise of temperature is encountered during 1-15th April. The rise in temperature during 1st February to 15th March will also be harmful for early sown wheat. Rise in temperature during Jan 1- 14th February will be beneficial for timely and late sown wheat. Rise in temperature during February 15 to March 15 will be beneficial for timely sown wheat. The timely sown wheat will be benefited more by 2°C increase in temperature above normal during 1st February to 15th March.

The increase in temperature by 2.5°C will be harmful if it occurs during 16-31st March in early, timely and late sown wheat, the effect however, decreased delay in sowing. The reduction will also be noticed in late sown wheat if this rise of temperature is encountered during 16-30th April. Rise in temperature during 1st to 31st January will be beneficial for all the three date of sowing, out of which late sown wheat will be benefited more.

Fortnightly increase in temperature by 3 °C above normal will be harmful if it occurs during 16-31st March in early, timely and late sown wheat. The reduction will be noticed in late sown wheat if this rise of temperature is encountered during 1-15th April. The rise of temperature during 1-15th March will cause reduction in yield in early sown wheat. Rise in temperature during 1st Jan - 15th March will be beneficial for timely and late sown wheat.

Late sown wheat will be benefitted the most with 3 °C above normal rise in temperature if this occurs during January, second fortnight of February and 1st fortnight of March.

Fig 4.1 Rise in temperature at each fortnight intervals by 0.5 °C (a), 1.5 °C (b), and 2.5 °C (c) and normal before and after vs. yield (kg/ha)

4.1.2 Performance of wheat under rise of temperature for each fortnightly, effect of additional nitrogen and irrigation

Application of additional nitrogen in timely sown wheat will be beneficial to reduce the effect of 0.5 °C rise in temperature during 1-15th April wherein around 300 kg reduction in yield would be nullified and around 100 kg/ha additional grain yield will be obtained. The additional irrigation will reduce the effect of rising temperature during same period and will enhance the grain yield of early sown wheat by 600 kg/ha. In timely sown wheat, additional nitrogen application will prove marginally beneficial to reduce the impact of 1.0 °C temperature during 1st to 15th January. Additional irrigation would have no effect to modify the impact of rise in temperature as far as grain yield in wheat is concerned.

In timely and late sown wheat, nitrogen application will prove beneficial to reduce the impact of rise in temperature (1.5 °C) during 1st to 15th January. The additional irrigation will not prove beneficial for reducing the impact of rising temperature during different fortnight intervals. To reduce the effect of rise in temperature by 2°C during different fortnight intervals, application of additional nitrogen will be beneficial for early and timely sown wheat. The irrigation however will have no effect.

Application of additional nitrogen and additional irrigation will have no effect for containing the impact of 2.5 °C rise in temperature during different fortnight intervals. Application of additional nitrogen will be helpful to contain the effect of 3 °C rise in temperature during 1st to 15th Jan in timely sown wheat. Additional irrigation will have no effect. The results are summarized in Table 4.2

Table 4.2 Summary of impact (+/-) of intra seasonal rise in temperature during different fortnight intervals in wheat

Temp. rise	Early sowing		Timely sowing		Late sowing		Remarks
	Positive	Negative	Positive	Negative	Positive	Negative	
0.5 °C	-Nil-	1 st fortnight March	February /1 st fortnight March	1 st fortnight April	2 nd fortnight January/ March		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • More beneficial to timely and late sown wheat than early sown • Additional nitrogen: in timely sown wheat will reduce the impact during 1-15th April with 100kg/ha additional grain yield • Additional irrigation: in early sown wheat will reduce the impact during 1-15th April with 600kg/ha additional grain yield
1.0 °C	-Nil-	2 nd fortnight March	2 nd fortnight of January/ 1 st fortnight February	2 nd fortnight March		1 st fortnight April	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Timely sown wheat will be more benefitted • Additional nitrogen: timely sown will be marginally benefitted during first fortnight of January • Additional irrigation: will have no effect
1.5 °C	-Nil-	2 nd fortnight March	1 st fortnight January /1 st fortnight February/ 1 st fortnight March	2 nd fortnight March	1 st fortnight January/2 nd fortnight February/1 st fortnight March	1 st fortnight April	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Temperature rise during 15th Feb-15th March in late sown wheat will be more benefitted • Additional nitrogen: will be beneficial for timely and late sown during first fortnight of January • Additional irrigation: no effect
2.0 °C	-Nil-	2 nd fortnight March	2 nd fortnight of February/1 st fortnight March	2 nd fortnight March /1 st January - 14 th February/15 th February- 15 th March		1 st January -14 th February/ 2 nd fortnight March /1 st fortnight April	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Increase in temperature during 16-31st March will cause reduction in all the dates and reduction decreases with delay in sowing. Timely sown wheat is benefitted more if temperature rise is encountered during 1st Feb to 15th March • Additional nitrogen: beneficial for early and timely sown • Additional irrigation: no effect
2.5 °C	January	2 nd fortnight March	January	2 nd fortnight March	January	2 nd fortnight March /1 st fortnight April	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Increase in temperature during 16-31st March causes reduction in all the dates and reduction decreases with delay in sowing. • Timely sown wheat is benefitted more if temperature rise is encountered during 1st Feb to 15th March. Rise in temperature during 1-31st Jan will be beneficial for all the three dates, one of which late sown wheat will be benefitted the most. • Additional nitrogen and additional irrigation will have no effect
3 °C	1 st fort-night January & February	1 st & 2 nd fortnight March	1 st January - first fortnight March	2 nd fortnight March	1 st January - 1 st fortnight March	2 nd fortnight March /1 st fortnight April	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Additional nitrogen will be helpful to contain the effect of 3.0°C rise in temperature during 1-15th January in timely sowing wheat. • additional irrigation will have no effect

Chapter 5

Agromet advisories and contingency plans for Wheat

5.1 Agro Advisory Service

Agro Advisory Service Units (AASU) program for dissemination of medium range weather forecast from the National Centre for Medium Range Weather Forecast (NCMRWF) was raised from 83 Units during early 1990s at the erstwhile NARP Centres of ICAR located in the different agro climatic regions to presently 127 Units. AASU at Palampur Centre was established during 1992. Based on the MRWF received twice a week, weather based agro advisories are prepared by these units located at the state Agricultural University Research Centres for dissemination to the farming community through various communication media. Since then this centre was/is also sending specific advisories mostly once in a week based on a forecasted weather event having potential impact on agricultural activities/ managements. Some of the advisories on sowing, irrigation/drainage, applications of agrochemicals and harvesting/threshing windows, issued to the farmers by AICRPAM, Palampur Centre through the National Mobile Governance Initiative, Mobile Seva, Ministry of communication and Information Technology, Government of India (<http://esms.mgov.gov.in>) during past couple of years on wheat are listed in Table 5.1 to 5.4.

Table 5.1 Advisories suggesting sowing windows

S. No.	Advisories
1.	भूमि में उचित मात्रा में नमी होने की दशा में समय पर उगाए जाने वाली गेहूँ की एच0 पी0 डब्लू0 155, 211, 236, वी0 एल0 804, 832, 907, एच0एस0 507 किस्मों में से किसी एक का चुनाव करके इसकी बिजाई 15 नवम्बर तक पूरी करें।
2.	प्रदेश के लगभग सभी पर्वतीय जिलों के अनेक स्थानों पर बर्फ के साथ बारिश होने की सम्भावना है। मैदानी व मध्यवर्ती इलाकों में भी आने वाले 2-3 दिनों में वर्षा का अनुमान है। किसानों को सलाह दी जाती है कि गेहूँ की बिजाई अतिशीघ्र पूरी कर लें।
3.	ऊना, हमीरपुर और मण्डी जिलों में आगामी चार-पांच दिनों तक मौसम साफ रहने का अनुमान है। अतः सलाह दी जाती है कि सरसों व इस समय लगाई जाने वाली गेहूँ की किस्मों की बुआई कर के भूमि के अंदर उपलब्ध नमी का पूरा फायदा उठाएँ। सुखाने वाले घास की कटाई भी शुरू कर लें। नवजात बछड़ों व दुधारू पशुओं को सुबह व शाम पड़ने वाली ठण्ड से बचा कर रखें।
4.	आगामी चार दिनों तक प्रदेश के सभी जिलों में हल्के बादलों के साथ मौसम शुष्क रहेगा तथा पहले दो-तीन दिनों तक तापमान में कमी और इसके बाद तापमान में सुधार होगा। भूमि में उचित मात्रा में नमी होने की दशा में समय पर उगाए जाने वाली गेहूँ की किस्मों की बिजाई अतिशीघ्र पूरी करें।
5.	आगामी तीन-चार दिन में प्रदेश के लगभग सभी जिलों में मौसम साफ़ बने रहने की सम्भावना है। अतः सलाह दी जाती है कि सरसों व इस समय लगाई जाने वाली गेहूँ की किस्मों की बुआई कर के भूमि के अंदर उपलब्ध नमी का पूरा फायदा उठाएँ।
6.	आगामी तीन-चार दिनों तक प्रदेश के लगभग सभी जिलों में मौसम साफ़ रहने तथा तापमान सामान्य बने रहने की सम्भावना है। अतः सलाह दी जाती है कि गेहूँ की समय पर लगाई जाने वाली किस्मों की बुआई कर के भूमि के अंदर उपलब्ध नमी का पूरा फायदा उठाएँ।
7.	आगामी तीन-चार दिनों तक प्रदेश के लगभग सभी जिलों में मौसम साफ़ रहने तथा तापमान सामान्य बने रहने की सम्भावना है। अतः सलाह दी जाती है कि गेहूँ की समय पर लगाई जाने वाली किस्मों की बुआई कर के भूमि के अंदर उपलब्ध नमी का पूरा फायदा उठाएँ।
8.	प्रदेश के सभी जिलों में एक-दो दिनों के बाद मौसम साफ़ होने तथा मैदानी इलाकों में तापमान में सुधार की सम्भावना है। प्रदेश-भर में पिछले दो-तीन दिनों में व्यापक और पर्याप्त वर्षा दर्ज की गई है अतः भूमि में वर्षा के कारण उपलब्ध नमी का भरपूर लाभ उठाने हेतु जो किसान किसी कारणवश गेहूँ की बिजाई नहीं कर पाये हैं वे पछेती बीजी जाने वाली गेहूँ की किस्मों की बिजाई अतिशीघ्र पूरी कर लें।

Table 5.2 Advisories suggesting irrigation/ drainage

S. No.	Advisories
1.	प्रदेश में 1 अक्टूबर से 27 नवम्बर तक 36.2 मि. मी. वर्षा दर्ज की गई जोकि सामान्य से 38% कम थी। आगामी चार दिनों तक प्रदेश के सभी जिलों में तापमान में गिरावट के साथ मौसम शुष्क रहने की संभावना है। सलाह दी जाती है कि जहाँ सिंचाई की सुविधा उपलब्ध हो, वहाँ पर फसलों को सूखे व गिरते तापमान से बचाने के लिए सिंचाई अवश्य करें।
2.	1 मार्च को प्रदेश के अधिकांश जिलों में भारी बारिश दर्ज की गई। खेतों में पानी खड़ा होने से फसलों में नुकसान की सम्भावना बनी रहती है अतः किसानों को सलाह दी जाती है कि खेतों से पानी की निकासी का उचित प्रबंध करें।

Table 5.3 Advisories suggesting application of fertilizers, insecticides & pesticides

S. No.	Advisories
1.	आने वाले 2-3 दिनों में प्रदेश के विभिन्न जिलों जैसे चम्बा, लाहौल-स्पिति, कुल्लू, काँगड़ा और किन्नौर में हल्की से मध्यम बारिश होने की सम्भावना है। किसानों को सलाह दी जाती है कि बरानी क्षेत्रों में नाइट्रोजन की शेष मात्रा वर्षा होने पर ही डालें।
2.	आने वाले चार दिनों में प्रदेश के मैदानी और कम ऊंचाई वाले क्षेत्रों में वर्षा और ऊंचाई वाले क्षेत्रों में बर्फवारी और तापमान में कुछ गिरावट आने की सम्भावना है। किसानों को सलाह दी जाती है कि नाइट्रोजन की शेष मात्रा वर्षा के बाद ही डालें।
3.	गेहूँ में पीला रतुआ रोग के लिए मौसम अति अनुकूल है। प्रदेश से सटे पंजाब और हरियाणा के कुछ इलाकों में इस रोग के लक्षण पाए गये हैं। अनुकूल मौसम के चलते इस रोग के हिमाचल प्रदेश में भी फैलने की सम्भावना है। किसानों को सलाह दी जाती है कि वे सतर्क रहें और रोगग्रस्त पत्ते को हाथ से छूने से यदि पीले रंग के बीजाणु दिखें तो परोपीकोनाजोल 1 मि. ली. प्रति लीटर की दर से छिड़काव करें। सलाह दी जाती है कि इस संदेश को अधिक से अधिक किसानों से जनहित में साझा करें।
4.	आने वाले 3-4 दिनों में हल्के बादलों के साथ मौसम शुष्क रहने तथा तापमान में सुधार होने की सम्भावना है। खरपतवारों में 2-3 पत्ते की अवस्था आने पर आइसोप्रोट्यूरान 70 ग्राम 30 लीटर पानी में घोल कर प्रति कनाल दर से छिड़काव करें। नत्रजन खाद की एक तिहाई मात्रा भी गेहूँ के खेत में डालें। अच्छे मौसम और मिटटी में पर्याप्त नमी का पूरा लाभ उठाएं और फसलों की उचित देख-भाल करें।
5.	आने वाले 2 दिनों में प्रदेश के मैदानी इलाकों में हल्की बर्षा तथा पहाड़ी इलाकों में बर्फवारी के साथ तापमान में कमी आने की सम्भावना है। जिन इलाकों में गेहूँ के खरपतवारों में 2-3 पत्ते की अवस्था आ गयी हो और इनके नियंत्रण के लिए छिड़काव न किया हो, वहां पर बर्षा के बाद मिटटी में पर्याप्त नमी का लाभ उठाते हुए आइसोप्रोट्यूरान 70 ग्राम 30 लीटर पानी में घोल कर प्रति कनाल दर से छिड़काव करें।
6.	प्रदेश में आने वाले तीन-चार दिनों में मौसम प्रायः साफ रहने तथा तापमान में कुछ सुधार आने की सम्भावना है। खरपतवारों में 2-3 पत्ते की अवस्था आने पर आइसोप्रोट्यूरान 70 ग्राम 30 लीटर पानी में घोल कर प्रति कनाल दर से छिड़काव करें। अच्छे मौसम और मिटटी में पर्याप्त नमी का पूरा लाभ उठाएं और फसलों की उचित देख-भाल करें।

Table 5.4 Advisories issued to suggest harvesting and threshing windows

S. No.	Advisories
1.	आगामी दो दिनों के बाद हल्के बादलों के साथ मौसम शुष्क रहने की सम्भावना है। सलाह दी जाती है की गेहूँ की कटाई करके सुरक्षित भण्डारण कर लें।
2.	आगामी दो दिनों में प्रदेश के विभिन्न जिलों में मौसम साफ़ रहने की सम्भावना है। सलाह दी जाती है की पूरी पक्की हुई गेहूँ की कटाई करके सुरक्षित भण्डारण कर लें।
3.	5 मई, 2013 तक साफ़ मौसम के साथ पूरी धूप खिलेगी। पक्की हुई गेहूँ की कटाई व गहाई पूरी कर लें।
4.	आगामी तीन दिनों तक प्रदेश के सभी जिलों में मौसम साफ़ रहने तथा तापमान सामान्य बने रहने की संभावना है। सलाह दी जाती है कि पकी हुई गेहूँ की कटाई व गहाई शीघ्र पूरी कर लें।
5.	आगामी दिनों तक प्रदेश के अधिकतर जिलों में मौसम खराब रहने तथा तापमान में गिरावट की संभावना है। सलाह दी जाती है कि कटी हुई गेहूँ की फसल का सुरक्षित भंडारण कर लें।
6.	14 मई के बाद 17 मई तक प्रदेश के अधिकांश जिलों में हल्के बादलों के साथ मौसम शुष्क रहेगा। किसान इस शुष्क मौसम का लाभ उठाते हुए पकी हुई गेहूँ की फसल की कटाई व गहाई अतिशीघ्र पूरी कर लें।
7.	आगामी दो-तीन दिन तक प्रदेश के अधिकांश जिलों में हल्के बादलों के साथ मौसम साफ़ रहने की संभावना है। सलाह दी जाती है कि गेहूँ की पकी हुई फसल की कटाई व गहाई शीघ्र पूरी कर के दानों को अच्छी तरह से सूखा कर सुरक्षित भंडारण करें।
8.	23 मई के बाद अधिकांश जिलों में हल्की वर्षा की सम्भावना है। अतः कटी हुई गेहूँ की गहाई अतिशीघ्र पूरी करें।
9.	ऊना, हमीरपुर व बिलासपुर जिलों में अगले चार-पांच दिनों तक मौसम शुष्क रहेगा। किसानों को सलाह दी जाती है कि पक कर तैयार हो चुकी गेहूँ की कटाई व गहाई अतिशीघ्र पूरी कर लें।
10.	प्रदेश के सभी जिलों में 6 तारीख तक हल्के बादलों के साथ मौसम शुष्क रहेगा। इसके बाद अगले तीन-चार दिनों तक कुछ स्थानों पर हल्की वर्षा की सम्भावना है। किसानों को सलाह दी जाती है कि गेहूँ की कटाई व गहाई का काम मौसम की परिस्थिति के अनुसार ही करें।
11.	आगामी तीन-चार दिनों तक प्रदेश के अधिकतर जिलों में हल्की से दरम्यानी बारिश की सम्भावना है। किसानों को सलाह दी जाती है कि गेहूँ की गहाई तथा अन्य कृषि सम्बन्धी कार्यों को मौसम की परिस्थिति के अनुसार ही करें।
12.	आगामी चार-पांच दिनों तक प्रदेश के सभी जिलों में मौसम साफ़ रहने की सम्भावना है। अतः किसानों को सलाह दी जाती है कि गेहूँ की कटाई व गहाई का शेष काम अतिशीघ्र पूरा करें।
13.	आगामी दो-तीन दिनों तक प्रदेश के अधिकांश जिलों में हल्के बादलों के साथ मौसम शुष्क रहेगा क्योंकि उपरोक्त समय के उपरान्त हल्की वर्षा की सम्भावना है। अतः सलाह दी जाती है कि जिन किसानों ने गेहूँ की कटाई व गहाई का काम अभी पूरा नहीं किया है उसे अतिशीघ्र पूरा करें।

A case study on impact assessment carried out on the farmers' fields who adopted agro advisories compared to those who have not followed advisories indicated that weather based agro advisories gave 1-7 percent higher net return in wheat crop (GGSN *et al.*, 2010).

5.2 Contingency plans for wheat

Contingency planning is increasingly being realized as an important component of preparedness to minimize the adverse impact of weather aberrations on agriculture and allied sectors in the context of increasing climatic variability. Prior to any centralised systematic method at CSKHPKV sporadic local efforts were being made to prepare contingency plans. One such example for six scenarios of onset of winter rains is presented in Table 6.5.

Table 5.5 Chance of occurrence of six scenarios of winter rains and contingent crop plan for mid-hill region in Himachal Pradesh during *rabi* season

Scenario	Chances of occurrence (% of years)	Contigent Plan
Onset before 15 Oct	10	Toria + gobi sarson, Gobi sarson (var. Sheetal) and Wheat var.616
Onset between 15 Oct-15 Nov	10	Normal package of practice
Onset between 15 Nov-15 Dec	20	Wheat var. HPW-42 and HS-295
Onset between 15 -31 Dec	20	Wheat var. HPW-42 (Aradhana)
Onset between 1-15 Jan	30	Wheat var. HPW-42 (Aradhana)
Onset after 15 Jan	10	Wheat var. HS-295, HPW-42 (Aradhana) and oats for fodder

State wise technical documents comprising of suggested contingency measures related to crops were urgently required in the country. Realising the importance of increasing losses in different sectors of agriculture vis-à-vis rising extreme weather events, the department of Agriculture and Cooperation, Ministry of Agriculture, Government of India, sponsored a country-wide effort under the aegis of ICAR. A standard template for preparation of district level contingency plans was formulated by CRIDA, Hyderabad and shared with all the SAUs. Several workshops were organized at CRIDA, Hyderabad, CSWCRTI, and Dehradun and finally at CSK HPKV, Palampur to finalize the district level plans for Himachal Pradesh which was published during October, 2013 (Prasad *et al.*, 2013).

Suggested contingency measures for management of wheat crop during aberrant conditions of rainfall, temperature, drought, irrigation water availability, heat wave, frost, high velocity winds etc. during different phases of crop for both rain fed and irrigated condition are presented Table 6.6 to 6.10.

Table 5.6 Plans for delay in onset of winter rains by 2, 4 & 6 weeks

Rainfall abnormality	Suggested contingency measures		Agronomic measures
	Normal cropping system	New cropping system	
Delay in winter showers by 2 weeks (First week of Jan.)	Maize-Wheat/ Barley/Oat Maize –Toria - Wheat Mize+ Pulses- Wheat +Sarson Rice- Wheat Mash- Wheat Tomato/Capsicum-Wheat Okra-Wheat	In Zone I & II	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Increase seed rate by 25% • Reduce the nitrogen fertilizer dose by 25% • Close spacing • Addition of organic manures (FYM/compost) to the soil at least 5-10t/ha. • Adopt soil moisture conservation measures with locally available Mulch.
		In Zone III (High Hills)	
Delay in winter showers by 4 weeks (3 rd week of Jan.)	Maize-Wheat/ Barley/Oat Maize –Toria - Wheat Mize+ Pulses- Wheat +Sarson Rice- Wheat Mash- Wheat Tomato/Capsicum-Wheat Okra-Wheat	In Zone I & II	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Increase seed rate by 25% • Reduce the nitrogen fertilizer dose by 25% • Close spacing • Addition of organic manures (FYM/compost) to the soil at least 5-10t/ha. • Adopt soil moisture conservation measures with locally available Mulch.
Delay in winter showers by 6 weeks (2 nd week of Feb.)	Maize-Wheat/ Barley/Oat Maize –Toria - Wheat Maize-Pea/Bean-Potato Mize+ Pulses- Wheat +Sarson Rice- Wheat Mash- Wheat Tomato/Capsicum-Wheat Okra-Wheat	In Zone I & II	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Increase seed rate by 25% • Reduce the nitrogen fertilizer dose by 25% • Close spacing • Addition of organic manures (FYM/compost) to the soil at least 5-10t/ha. • Adopt soil moisture conservation measures with locally available Mulch.

Table 5.7 Plans for mid-season drought occurring during different phenophases

Conditions	Suggested contingency measures			
Mid-season drought (long dry spell, consecutive 2 weeks rainless (<2.5 mm) period)	Major farming situation	Normal crop/cropping system	Change in crop/cropping system including variety	Agronomic measures
At vegetative stage	Medium rainfall, Medium deep to deep, loamy-skeletal soils	Maize-wheat Paddy-wheat	Create dust mulch through frequent interculture	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Undertake re-sowing with late sown varieties of wheat like VL 892, Raj 3777, HS 420, if germination is <50% of optimum • Undertake gap filling if plant population is <70% of optimum • Use weeds as mulch • Creating dust mulch by hand racking • Spray 2% urea or 1% NPK (soluble fertilizer) during the dry spell • Prepare ridges and furrows • Apply lifesaving irrigation from water harvesting structures
	Medium rainfall, Shallow, sandy soils	Maize-wheat		
	Medium rainfall, Medium deep to deep, loamy soils	Maize- Toria – Wheat Mash-Wheat		
	Shallow to medium deep loamy soils, and deep loamy-skeletal soils to deep loamy soils	Wheat, Barley Maize - Barley/Wheat	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Cut the crop to reduce population • Carry out weeding and inter culture 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Spray 1% urea during the dry spell • Carry out weeding and their <i>in-situ</i> mulching • Adopt soil moisture conservation measures with locally available mulch materials
	Upland rain fed loamy, coarse, loamy skeletal deep to medium deep soils	Wheat	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Cut the crop to reduce plant population • Remove weeds 	Foliar spray of nutrients
	Upland	Wheat	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Reduce plant population by 10-20% and carry out weeding 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Provide life saving irrigation with rain water stored in water harvesting structures from adjoining fields • Spray nutrients on foliage

Mid-season drought (long dry spell) or Terminal drought (Early withdrawal of winter rains)	Medium rainfall, medium deep to deep, loamy-skeletal soils	Maize-wheat	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Apply life saving irrigation from the water harvested from water harvesting structures • If the damage is severe, harvest for fodder or harvest at physiological maturity 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Apply foliar spray of Nitrogen • Apply lifesaving irrigation
	At flowering/ fruiting stage	Medium rainfall, shallow, sandy soils	Paddy-wheat	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Apply lifesaving irrigation from the water harvested from water harvesting structures • Use wheat crop as fodder or allow domestic animals to graze the wheat crop
	Medium rainfall, medium deep to deep, loamy soils	Maize-wheat		
	Shallow to medium deep loamy soils, and deep loamy-skeletal soils to deep loamy soils	Wheat, Barley Maize - Barley/Wheat	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • If crop stand is poor then use of crop as fodder or • Harvest at physiological maturity 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Spray 1% urea during the dry spell • Apply life saving irrigation through the water collected from the water harvesting structures • Adopt soil moisture conservation measures with locally available mulch materials • Carry out weeding and their <i>in-situ</i> mulching
	Upland rain fed loamy, coarse, loamy skeletal deep to medium deep soils	Wheat	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Apply life saving irrigation if available • If crop stand is poor then use crop as fodder 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • If crop is very poor use it as fodder • Foliar spray of N if plant stand is adequate • Prepare land for sowing of <i>Kharif</i> crop
	Upland	Wheat	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Carry out mulching in crop rows if possible • Dust mulch through frequent inter culture • Apply life saving irrigation from water harvesting structures • Apply life saving irrigation from water harvesting structures if possible • Reduce plant population by 10 – 20% 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Apply foliar spray 2% of urea during the dry spell

Table 5.8 Plans for management of drought under irrigated conditions

Condition	Suggested contingency measures			
	Major farming situation	Normal crop/cropping system	Change in crop/cropping system including variety	Agronomic measures
Lack of inflow of water into tanks due to insufficient /delayed onset of rains	Low land tank fed	Wheat Rice - Wheat	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Sow late sown varieties viz., HS 490,VL 892, Raj 3777 Wheat + Mustard (RCC 4), Wheat + Gobhi sarson (Neelam, Sheetal) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Apply irrigation only at critical stages (CRI, flowering and dough stage), Popularize split application of N
	Upland tank fed			
Delayed/ limited release of water in canals due to low rainfall	Shallow to medium deep loamy soils, and deep loamy-skeletal soils to deep loamy soils (Irrigated)	Wheat Rice - Wheat	Wheat + Gram Wheat + Gobhi Sarson	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Intercropping Conserve <i>in-situ</i> soil moisture Apply life saving irrigation
	Irrigated loamy, coarse, loamy skeletal deep to medium deep soils		Shift to late sown varieties viz., HS 490,VL 892 Wheat + Mustard (RCC 4) Wheat + Gobhi sarson (Neelam)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Irrigation only at critical stages (CRI, flowering and dough stage) Popularization of split application of nitrogen
Insufficient groundwater recharge due to low rainfall	Tube well irrigation system	Wheat Rice - Wheat	Sowing of early maturing and drought resistant wheat variety viz., VL 829	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Zero till sowing of wheat crop, Irrigation only at critical stages (CRI, flowering and dough stage), Keep fields weed free by carry out <i>In-situ</i> mulching of weeds

Table 5.9 Plans for management of unusual rains (untimely, unseasonal etc.) both for rain fed and irrigated situations

Condition	Suggested contingency measure			
	Vegetative stage	Flowering stage	Crop maturity stage	Post-harvest
Continuous high rainfall in a short span leading to water logging	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Apply additional dose of nitrogen (25kg/ha) to remove deficiency of nitrogen (yellowing) caused due to leaching Drain out the water completely 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Drain out the water completely Control the Rust/Blight Spray Propiconazol @0.1% during last week of February or first week of March to control rust 	Drain out the water completely	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> After threshing undertake complete drying of grains under sun to ensure no fungal infection occurs If rains continue take to safe storage place and ensure 12-14% moisture in grains before storage
Heavy rainfall with high speed winds in a short span	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Drain out excess water Carry out intercultural operations to control weeds and improve soil aeration Apply additional fertilizer dose to regain lost vigor 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Drain out the excess water Carry out intercultural operations to control weeds and improve soil aeration 	Ensure complete drainage of water	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Drain out the excess water Apply additional fertilizer dose to regain lost vigor Harvest the produce on clear sunny day
Outbreak of pests and diseases due to unseasonal rains	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Leaf blight: (Apply Thiram 3 gm / kg of seed) Apply additional dose of Nitrogen (25kg/ha) to remove deficiency of nitrogen 	Karnal bunt: (Apply Tilt 25 EC @200ml) Yellow rust: (Apply Tilt 25 EC @200ml)	Completely drain off the water and harvest the crop, if physiologically matured	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Safe storage against storage pest and diseases Store in warehouse Cover the produce with polythene sheet Dry the grains up to 10-12% moisture

Table 5.10 Plans for management for extreme events (Heat wave / Cold wave/Frost/Hailstorm)

Extreme event type	Suggested contingency measure			
	Seedling / nursery stage	Vegetative stage	Reproductive stage	At harvest
Heat wave	Apply irrigation if available to combat the effect of high temperature			
Cold wave	Apply light and frequent irrigation wherever irrigation facilities are available			
Frost	Apply light and frequent irrigation using sprinklers if available and create smoke during night	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Apply irrigation using sprinklers if available Burn crop residue around the crop Spray of H₂SO₄ @0.1% 		Not applicable
Hailstorm	At harvest stage, harvest the crop according to weather condition and weather forecast, stake the produce in the safe or sheltered places in the event of unseasonal hailstorm /rainfall			
Storm/ high velocity wind	At harvest stage, Harvest the crop according to weather condition and weather forecast, stake the produce in the safe or sheltered places in the event of storm/high velocity wind and rainfall			

Implementation of contingency plans are mentioned above are still at infancy stage in India and it requires elaborated arrangements for their effective implementation. Some of the important issues requiring urgent attention are given below:

5.3 Issues involved for implementation of contingency plans in wheat

To implement the contingency plans, extensive planning both at the district and state levels is required which needs to be coordinated and facilitated by Government of India. Currently, at the Government of India level, the crop weather watch group under the Ministry of Agriculture and Farmers' Welfare monitors the weather situation and helps the ministry to coordinate the preparedness for droughts and other contingencies. The current efforts are basically to save the crop and minimize the losses with some broad interventions at the agro-climatic zone or district level. Though the Government may wait for certain time before declaration of drought, the district team needs to gear up as the information on rainfall and progress of sowings are collected continuously during the season. The district level contingency plans (DLCPs) provide exhaustive details of the alternate crops and varieties in case of delay in winter rains for raising wheat crop within the district. With the advance planning and organizing inputs in time, these plans can help the farmers and reduce the losses in the affected areas.

Weather forecast as a base to plan contingencies

Currently, IMD gives short and medium range forecast at the district level for the next 2 to 5 days period. Since, this forecast is not provided with sufficient lead time to implement the contingencies plans, therefore advance forecast of winter rains must be issued on the pattern of monsoon forecast which will facilitate the implementation of these plans well in time. In a study conducted by AICRPAM, Palampur Centre, it was found that average rainfall during the years following El-Nino was not only higher but also had more likelihood of getting above average rains during subsequent winters. Rainfall during winter season in Himachal Pradesh was higher in nine out of 10 selected districts; six districts showed more than 20 per cent increase in rainfall (Prasad *et al.*, 2014). Such type of tele-signals can be used for issuing the advance forecast of the winter rains.

Special *rabi* meetings

Currently, the Government of India and the states hold *rabi* planning meetings to draw out the overall strategy and production targets for the year. However, it is suggested that immediately after this, a separate meeting may be held at the State level exclusively focused on

coping with weather aberrations and how to tackle the contingencies, if arisen including the preparedness of the departments with inputs and the strategies to dovetail funds under different schemes. They should meet as frequently as possible and draw up the action plans as the season progresses and the weather situation unfolds.

In season review and implementation

Once a given district or agro-climatic zone is identified either for drought or floods prone, the state and district administration may constantly review the situation during the season and take appropriate steps for effective implementation of the DLCPs. In case of drought, the progressive rainfall deficits and the effective implementation on crop situation coming from the blocks/districts will be used to execute the plan at appropriate locations. For mobilizing inputs particularly seed of alternative crops and varieties as listed in the DLCPs, the district-wise seed production and storage plan need to be put in place as a medium term strategy. In case of unseasonal rains and prolonged drought at time of sowing, suitable agro- advisors are to be given by the agricultural universities and the department of agriculture through the available dissemination channels so that farmers can take appropriate and timely decisions regarding whether to harvest a crop or postpone it, or to apply irrigation or to withhold etc., so that the losses are minimized.

Seed production, storage and disposal

While the above steps guide the implementation of DLCPs in the current season, some medium term strategies are required for enabling this implementation. The most important input is the seed of wheat crop and varieties that can be sown in case of delayed rains. Though, the agricultural universities and ICAR institutes have recommended several such crops and varieties for delayed sowing. To address this problem, the seeds of crops and varieties to be used in case of delayed winter rains have to be produced every year whether they are eventually used or not. In case the rains are normal and the seeds are not used, they may be disposed off as grain. Appropriate seed storage mechanism including godowns and fumigation systems have to be evolved along with the locations where seeds are to be stored depending on the cropping pattern in a region and the weather vulnerability.

Other associated Measures

There are a number of medium and long term strategies which are critical for sustained implementation of DLCPs when weather aberrations occur. These include the use of MGNREGA and IWMP programs for undertaking drought proofing works in a planned manner. Others include, rain water harvesting for supplemental irrigation and soil organic build up through biomass recycling so that the water holding capacity of the soil improves and the crops can cope up with the dry spells. Promoting weather insurance is another step which will minimize the risks to farmers due to weather aberrations. The issue of wild and stray animals has been attracting the attention of politicians, administrators and researchers during recent past in Himachal Pradesh. Since, this issue is discouraging the farmers to continue with the farming and also making farming grossly unprofitable. It is, therefore, suggested that some concrete measures must be urgently put in place immediately to manage the menace of these animals.

Fine tuning crop/agricultural management practices

Generalized management practices have been documented under DLCPs which needs refinement from time to time. Universities and Crop Commodity Institutes should start experiments for their refinements vis- á- vis technology demonstrations at Research stations and KVKs for which funding could be requisitioned from NICRA programme. Universities should also now start demonstrating technologies suggested under DLCPs every year so that in the event of aberrant weather situations these technologies are effectively field tested. Few years of such experimentation should automatically enable the Farm Scientists to modifying the Package of Practices (of various crops and animals) based on time tested DLCPs. While undertaking refinements in future, the contents of DLCPs must contain alternative crops (marigold, turmeric, colocasia, chillies and garlic etc.) which are least palatable for wild animals, fetch remunerative prices in the market and must possess ingrained content of climate resilience. Recommendations for alternative crops should come from the research institutions/ universities engaged in research and extension programs in the state.

Role of Kisan Call Centre and DD Kisan for dissemination of District Level Contingency Plans

It is becoming increasingly clear that the next leap will come from the information and the knowledge intensity transfer to the agriculture sector, together with the other traditional inputs and interventions. The real challenge before the policy makers is to overcome the information

asymmetry between farmers, villages, regions and country as a whole. With the decrease in the number of extension workers, there is a need to use the latest technologies for delivering extension services. Towards this, the erstwhile Department of Agriculture and Cooperation has been working on schemes to use both Mass-Media and telecom network for the delivery of extension services. One of the draw-backs experienced in the current human resource based extension service has been that the monitoring authorities are not able to get a clear feedback on the quality of extension services being delivered in the villages. But the Kisan Call Centre based extension service is delivering knowledge and information exactly as per the requirements of the farming community. The Kisan Call Centre scheme has been functioning since 21st January, 2004 with the objective to make agriculture knowledge available free of cost to the farmers as and when desired. This system helps keeping a record of what is being delivered to the farmers in terms of knowledge and information. This scheme is available throughout the country and at present the Call Centre services are available at a common toll free telephone number, 18001801551 which can be dialled from anywhere in the country between 7.00 AM to 10.00 PM except on Sundays and gazetted holidays, beyond these hours the calls are attended in the IVRS mode. The location is immaterial as the calls can originate from any village to land at a specific Call Centre and a specific query would be answered by an agriculture graduate knowing the local language and having adequate understanding of the local agricultural problems. The calls are received at 13 Call Centres wherein 116 Agriculture Graduates attend to answer the query of the farmers in the local language. 123 experts located in different parts of the country at State Agriculture Universities, ICAR institutes, State Department of Agriculture, Horticulture and other developments are answering the calls at Level –II. At present AICRPAM Palampur Centre also sends information on weather based farm management practices to the Kisan Call Centre, situated at Chandigarh for further dissemination to the farmers of Himachal Pradesh.

By launching ‘DD Kisan’ a 24-hour television channel on 26 May 2015, Indian Government achieved another mile stone. The channel has been dedicated to agriculture and allied sectors, which disseminates real-time information to farmers on weather, new farming techniques, water conservation and organic farming among other information. The channel promises live weather updates and host of other agriculture related practices including animal husbandry and market updates of agricultural produce. DD Kisan and Kisan Call Centres can be made most effective agents for the dissemination of information on agro-advisories and contingency plans.

Chapter 6

Summary

Wheat which is known as king of cereals is amongst the first cereals domesticated when agriculture came into existence in 7500 BC. The grains of this crop possess unique gluten content and associated bread making properties. It is used as food, feed and also has many industrial uses. This crop has widest adaptability with respect to climate, altitude and soil.

Himachal Pradesh shares nearly 10 percent of the acreage and 9 percent of the total production of wheat in India. The productivity of wheat in this state is around 28.4 tonnes ha⁻¹ with an area of 0.36 million hectare and production of 10.23 million tonnes (Government of Himachal Pradesh, 2012). Though, at present Himachal Pradesh is self-sufficient in wheat there is need to further increase its production and productivity to fulfill the requirement of teeming population and to maintain the state's share to national wheat production. Kangra, Mandi, Hamirpur, Una, Sirmaur, Bilaspur, Shimla, Solan, Kullu and Chamba account for over 99 per cent area and production of wheat.

The Agro-climatic characteristics wheat growing environment of the state indicate inadequate rains during sowing of wheat (mid- October to mid- December) which results in inadequate soil moisture which gives poor germination and seedling growth of the crop. Shallow coarse textured soils with undulating topography have poor soil moisture storage capacity leading to poor moisture availability during the season for this crop which is largely grown under rain fed conditions. Rainfall being inadequate and erratically distributed the critical stages of the crop lack sufficient soil moisture. Mid hills encounters low air and soil temperature conditions resulting in stunted growth during initial phases of crop growth. Below optimum use of fertilizers in the wake of inadequate moisture availability are some of the major issues responsible for fairly long crop duration (190-200 days) with low productivity of this crop in the state. Agro-meteorological information in respect of wheat crop has been reported in several research papers and continues to be reported and updated. The information contained therein was brought together and compiled in this bulletin. Some of the key points emanated from this manuscript are presented in this summary:

- The rain fed wheat completed its life cycle in more number of days (1-6 days depending upon the variety) as its emergence was delayed due to scarce soil moisture

at the time of sowing, yet effective number of days taken to complete tillering to heading stage was reduced by 9-15 days depending upon the variety.

- For emergence, rain fed wheat requires 325 heat units under normal sown conditions and 115 units under late sown conditions, whereas the irrigated wheat requires 115 heat units under normal sown conditions and 85 units under late sown conditions.
- In a prediction made using regression model indicate that up to 5th December, during grain filling the difference in observed and predicted values was mostly overestimated in irrigated whereas underestimated in rain fed conditions.
- In varieties, HPW 42, HPW 147 and HS 240 GDD was found to be the best index to predict 50 per cent grain filling.
- Under rain fed condition, the maximum wheat yields were realized with mean temperature in the range of 17.2 to 18.2 °C during reproductive phase. An increase in the temperature to 19.3 & 19.7 °C during reproductive phase resulted in drastic reduction in grain yield which were to the tune of 82.9 to 84.1 per cent.
- Under irrigated condition, the maximum wheat yields were realized with mean temperature in the range of 19.6 to 19.7 °C during reproductive phase. An increase in the temperature to 22.0 & 22.3 °C during reproductive phase resulted in drastic reduction in grain yield which were to the tune of 72.5 to 76.4 per cent.
- Pheno-thermal Index (PTI) was found to be nearly constant around a value of 10 degrees/day which was lower to that reported under Delhi conditions.
- Natural resource use efficiencies (HUE, RUE and WUE) were higher under late sown rain fed conditions compared to early sown rain fed conditions. The efficiency under irrigated conditions however decreased with delay in sowing.
- The optimum temperature value worked out for rain fed wheat in mid hill region of Himachal Pradesh indicate that these values were lower than reported by warmer and irrigated stations of the country which suggest that wheat crop has capacity to withstand higher temperature and can perform better under irrigated conditions.
- Variety VL 804 sown at four different locations, Bajaura, Malan, Shimla and Palampur under normal (4-11 November) and late (25 November-01 December) dates completed life cycle around 190-210 and 165-190 days, used around 1900-3300 and 1900-3000 heat units, produced around 23-48 and 19-50 q/ha, respectively under 450-500 mm rainfall.

- The yield reduction due to late sowing though was only 5.6% at Palampur but the reduction varied between 20.7 and 28.1 percent at Malan and Shimla stations, respectively.
- In general, 400-500 mm rainfall is proved more beneficial for the crop at Bajaura, Malan and Shimla stations to take the maximum benefit from the nitrogen applied.
- Chances of getting at least 10 mm weekly rainfall builds up only after meteorological week 49 (3-9th December). This amount is sufficient for proper germination of all winter-season crops. Therefore sowing of wheat should be ensured by the week 50 (10-16th December).
- Rainfall of December and January is beneficial for the early and timely sown wheat whereas January rainfall is beneficial for late sown wheat.
- Simulation studies, indicate that the temperature rise $\geq 1.0^{\circ}\text{C}$ during 2nd fortnight of March and later is harmful for wheat (all three sowing conditions viz., early, timely and late). The magnitude of the harmful effect will however, decrease with delay in sowing. Any temperature rise before this period till 1st January will have beneficial effect on all the three dates of sowing.
- Additional irrigation (6th irrigation) when applied to contain the effect of rise in temperature up to 0.5°C during 1st -15th April or equivalent amount of rainfall (75 mm) during same period will have a beneficial effect on early sown wheat (no effect of irrigation on further rise in temperature in early/timely/late sown wheat).
- The rainfall below 100 mm during February with lesser number of rainy days was found to be favorable for the yellow rust incidence and spread. The higher number of days with maximum temperature between $10-20^{\circ}\text{C}$ favoured yellow rust in different regions over the years. This observation provides sufficient evidence in favour of our earlier finding which indicated that the more number of days with maximum temperatures between $10-20^{\circ}\text{C}$ are favorable for rust incidence and its spread.

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Annexure 1

Normal weekly temperature (°C) in different wheat growing environments of Himachal Pradesh

Week No./stations	Akrot		Bajaura		Berthin		Dhaulakuan		Kangra		Malan		Palampur		Salooni		Shimla	
	Max.	Min.	Max.	Min.	Max.	Min.	Max.	Min.	Max.	Min.	Max.	Min.	Max.	Min.	Max.	Min.	Max.	Min.
40	32.2	20.1	29.2	12.6	30.9	18.5	30.9	17.4	30.5	19.6	28.5	17.2	26.0	15.3	26.5	14.4	22.7	13.1
41	31.3	17.4	28.5	10.2	29.9	15.3	30.6	14.9	29.5	17.1	27.9	15.9	25.5	14.3	26.1	14.4	21.9	12.3
42	30.7	15.3	26.8	8.0	29.2	13.3	29.7	12.7	28.6	15.1	27.2	14.5	24.6	13.1	25.5	13.5	20.8	10.9
43	29.9	14.3	25.9	6.6	27.9	11.1	28.4	11.1	27.5	12.9	26.1	13.2	23.7	12.2	24.1	12.6	20.1	10.3
44	29.2	13.2	26.0	5.8	27.1	9.7	27.9	10.2	27.1	12.2	26.0	12.6	23.2	11.6	24.5	12.6	19.4	9.8
45	28.1	12.1	24.4	4.7	26.5	8.7	27.0	9.3	26.1	11.3	25.5	11.8	22.0	10.6	24.1	12.5	18.6	9.0
46	26.8	10.7	23.7	3.4	25.9	7.1	26.1	8.1	24.6	10.4	23.8	10.7	21.2	9.5	23.6	11.8	18.0	8.6
47	25.8	9.6	22.0	2.5	24.3	6.1	25.0	7.1	23.7	9.0	22.8	10.0	20.4	8.5	22.7	11.4	17.0	7.6
48	24.3	8.5	20.9	1.3	23.5	5.1	23.9	5.7	23.0	7.3	21.9	8.7	19.0	7.4	22.2	11.1	16.3	6.7
49	24.1	7.9	20.1	1.0	22.8	4.5	23.4	4.9	22.5	7.4	21.4	8.0	19.1	7.4	21.2	11.2	16.2	7.1
50	22.3	8.0	18.0	1.0	20.5	4.6	22.0	5.0	20.8	7.1	19.8	7.7	17.7	6.7	20.3	10.3	14.3	5.5
51	21.9	6.8	17.5	0.6	20.7	4.0	21.5	4.3	20.7	6.0	19.3	7.1	17.4	6.2	20.0	9.9	14.4	5.6
52	20.3	5.4	16.6	0.3	19.3	3.1	20.2	3.7	19.4	4.5	18.7	6.2	16.0	5.1	18.7	9.2	13.1	4.3
1	18.1	5.3	15.5	0.6	17.9	3.4	18.9	4.5	18.1	4.7	17.1	5.3	15.2	4.7	18.4	8.3	12.1	3.6
2	19.6	6.0	15.8	0.8	18.9	3.0	18.9	4.1	18.6	4.8	16.7	5.5	15.2	4.9	18.5	8.6	11.7	3.4
3	18.6	6.8	15.1	1.2	18.1	4.7	19.0	4.6	18.0	5.8	16.5	5.8	14.8	4.8	17.6	7.9	11.6	3.3
4	19.9	5.9	16.7	1.2	19.0	3.2	20.4	4.2	18.5	5.1	16.9	5.7	15.1	5.0	18.0	8.0	12.6	3.7
5	20.8	7.2	17.3	2.0	20.4	4.1	21.3	5.0	19.3	6.6	18.1	6.5	15.8	5.6	16.8	7.2	13.2	4.4
6	20.6	8.7	17.0	3.0	20.2	6.5	21.6	6.1	19.2	7.4	17.7	6.6	15.9	5.9	15.7	6.3	12.9	4.2
7	21.8	9.1	16.7	3.5	20.1	6.2	22.1	6.7	19.6	8.1	18.1	7.0	16.5	6.5	15.9	6.7	12.7	4.0
8	23.4	9.9	18.3	4.0	22.9	7.3	23.2	7.1	21.3	9.3	20.2	7.8	17.4	6.7	17.0	7.4	13.6	4.6
9	24.6	10.3	19.3	4.6	24.1	7.9	24.1	7.8	22.6	8.7	20.9	8.6	18.3	8.1	18.1	8.1	15.0	6.0
10	26.3	10.9	21.4	5.3	25.8	8.0	26.3	8.6	23.9	10.0	22.3	9.1	19.8	9.2	19.0	8.1	16.5	7.0
11	28.2	12.7	21.7	5.9	26.8	9.3	27.3	10.0	25.3	10.4	23.2	9.9	20.6	9.9	19.7	8.3	17.2	7.8
12	29.3	14.2	22.4	6.6	28.7	10.5	29.0	11.3	27.3	11.6	25.3	11.0	21.7	10.6	19.0	7.7	17.8	8.5
13	30.6	15.0	23.5	7.2	28.2	11.0	29.7	11.4	27.9	12.5	25.9	11.2	22.9	11.8	19.6	8.1	18.9	9.5
14	32.4	15.9	24.7	7.9	30.0	11.4	31.9	12.3	29.2	13.9	26.7	12.4	24.2	12.7	20.0	8.2	20.1	10.5
15	34.4	17.5	26.1	8.7	31.9	12.2	33.1	13.2	30.6	13.9	27.8	13.1	25.5	13.9	20.0	8.2	21.0	11.6
16	34.7	18.5	27.1	9.3	32.5	13.9	34.3	14.8	31.0	15.2	29.1	13.4	26.6	15.0	19.8	7.9	22.2	12.6
17	36.4	19.5	27.8	10.3	33.2	14.1	35.8	15.6	32.8	16.7	30.7	14.9	27.9	16.5	20.4	8.7	23.3	13.5
18	37.0	21.1	28.7	11.4	34.2	15.9	36.2	17.2	33.1	17.9	31.9	16.2	28.9	17.2	20.6	8.8	24.0	14.4

Annexure 1a

Normal weekly rainfall in different wheat growing environments of Himachal Pradesh

Station	40	41	42	43	44	45	46	47	48	49	50	51	52	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12	13	14	15	16	17	18
Akrot	9.9	7.0	2.7	5.0	2.1	0.5	2.1	0.3	0.7	1.4	5.7	4.9	3.5	5.9	6	11.4	12.6	8.4	14.5	13.9	10.6	8.7	4.2	13.2	3.7	5.3	2.2	2.6	9.5	8.0	3.5
Arki	5.9	7.9	8.9	2.1	1.2	2.5	2.0	3.0	3.7	1.0	8.2	8.3	9.4	8.2	9.1	13.1	19.8	10.0	16.8	21.3	18.7	13.3	17.0	14.6	14.8	7.9	6.4	7.3	8.1	7.5	8.7
Bajaura	4.8	4.8	13.3	2.4	0.5	7.0	3.4	3.5	6.5	3.6	7.9	10.5	10.2	10.7	13.9	23.0	11.8	11.5	31.7	31.6	22.4	27.3	22.1	32.0	31.5	16.9	14.0	17.2	18.2	18.2	17.6
Banjar	4.3	5.4	5.4	4.0	1.6	6.1	2.1	5.0	2.9	2.5	6.9	9.6	9.1	10.5	13.8	24.5	12.6	10.7	26.8	22.4	19.5	29.3	14.8	27.1	20.1	17.5	10.4	14.4	15.5	17.2	14.7
Berthin	3.6	9.6	2.2	3.6	0.2	2.1	1.5	2.0	1.1	2.4	12.2	3.8	1.2	4.9	8.3	17.9	15.4	7.9	22.9	24.9	5.3	16.3	4.8	20.3	18.6	2.3	4.0	6.2	7.6	3.7	3.8
Bhoranj	10.5	4.4	1.3	1.0	1.7	1.5	0.8	0.2	0.1	2.1	3.9	2.0	6.8	5.8	9.3	20.5	15.8	10.1	25.3	25.6	4.8	22.6	7.3	10.9	13.9	3.3	10.9	4.6	7.5	2.9	9.2
Chachiot	3.6	11.4	0.6	0.0	0.7	0.0	1.1	1.4	0.4	2.0	8.2	0.8	0.6	5.3	5.4	19.5	4.4	4.6	21.9	11.1	3.5	9.9	10.7	5.8	7.2	8.2	0.7	4.8	19.5	4.9	10.9
Dehra	8.7	7.5	3.6	3.3	1.8	1.0	3.4	2.8	3.0	2.9	7.5	6.3	14.6	8.1	9.8	18.7	11.4	10.9	12.4	22.1	20.1	14.2	13.7	15.8	11.7	9.1	6.2	6.5	4.1	9.7	8.2
Dharamshala	15.3	11.9	8.0	5.7	4.2	2.9	4.5	3.3	6.8	3.7	10.2	11.5	20.5	20.5	16.2	26.6	23.3	19.3	23.7	33.7	25.8	30.5	24.8	27.8	29.5	17.0	14.0	17.2	13.5	12.7	13.3
Dhaulakuan	7.5	4.9	5.7	1.3	0.5	1.4	0.9	2.5	1.2	3.1	6.0	3.3	15.6	4.8	11.0	13.5	9.4	5.2	22.4	23.0	11.3	16.1	7.5	8.4	7.8	6.8	7.5	3.8	3.7	4.4	16.5
Ghumarwin	3.6	8.8	9.2	7.4	2.6	5.4	3.3	2.1	1.0	1.3	4.0	8.3	11.9	10.9	9.6	15.0	16.6	18.0	17.1	18.6	18.5	23.6	8.8	16.7	13.8	9.7	4.7	7.2	6.8	11.4	8.8
Hamirpur	5.4	10.8	7.3	4.9	2.5	1.0	2.6	4.2	2.6	2.2	7.4	6.3	12.9	8.1	14.5	13.0	19.8	15.8	17.9	29.8	16.0	18.8	13.7	16.8	16.5	7.9	7.7	8.4	7.7	10.0	9.7
Jogindenagar	16.4	11.5	5.0	2.0	1.9	6.3	2.2	0.5	2.0	5.1	17.3	7.0	0.4	13.1	8.6	32.1	19.4	12.8	31.5	28.2	11.2	30.8	12.1	24.4	19.8	10.0	2.6	15.9	39.4	12.4	3.4
Jubbals	11.4	10.8	5.8	5.7	3.8	1.7	1.1	3.2	2.7	1.8	7.5	14.5	12.1	9.2	14.8	18.7	27.5	14.2	18.1	22.9	20.3	23.5	16.4	16.8	20.9	15.9	9.6	9.9	17.1	15.9	18.4
Kandaghat	8.7	10.5	4.6	3.2	3.7	2.5	2.0	3.5	3.8	2.4	9.7	8.3	19.5	9.1	10.3	11.8	17.0	11.7	18.9	16.4	25.5	17.4	13.0	13.1	14.6	8.4	7.1	5.5	7.6	8.6	7.8
Kangra	5.9	9.2	5.1	4.6	1.7	2.9	9.8	2.7	0.6	3.2	8.1	4.0	6.8	3.9	9.5	27.3	10.9	16.0	27.8	16.0	17.6	18.8	4.3	17.3	8.9	7.1	11.4	7.0	14.1	5.8	5.6
Karsog	4.0	6.2	8.4	3.6	2.2	3.7	3.0	4.7	2.0	1.2	6.6	3.9	10.0	7.6	9.0	19.4	22.2	9.0	19.1	21.0	17.3	23.1	16.3	23.3	18.3	12.9	10.3	13.3	14.9	11.6	12.5
Kasuli	5.8	5.6	11.4	2.1	3.2	3.2	3.3	1.8	2.7	1.8	6.8	6.9	11.9	9.4	12.2	9.0	11.6	11.7	18.9	25.8	12.7	13.9	12.9	14.3	17.3	13.2	7.4	5.6	7.9	6.8	10.8
Keylong	3.1	3.8	3.2	2.4	2.3	5.4	4.5	4.1	2.0	4.3	7.3	8.1	16.1	6.3	8.0	14.0	12.5	6.9	18.9	20.5	23.7	22.0	22.4	26.9	31.9	13.2	14.2	15.9	12.0	12.2	10.2
Kotkhai	2.2	9.6	5.2	1.0	2.2	2.4	1.2	2.0	1.7	3.7	5.1	3.8	8.1	6.1	8.7	11.0	13.9	12.9	15.4	12.8	15.7	14.6	9.8	8.1	11.3	9.7	10.5	8.3	7.0	13.2	13.2
Kumarsain	3.7	7.8	3.2	2.9	3.1	3.2	3.1	1.8	2.7	2.4	4.5	6.8	9.1	7.1	8.6	15.0	13.6	15.0	18.2	14.2	13.7	15.0	10.1	14.0	17.6	7.8	9.4	10.8	10.5	12.5	12.4
Malan	12.3	6.9	2.5	4.3	0.3	3.5	8.1	0.6	0.5	1.6	13.5	2.9	4.2	7.4	16.4	24.7	15.4	14.5	28.9	22.0	14.2	22.0	8.3	15.6	15.2	6.5	4.7	4.0	12.4	6.5	4.8
Mandi	36.5	15.2	10.3	2.6	10.7	35.9	3.8	2.9	8.1	44.3	9.3	9.6	9.6	20.9	28.8	14.8	27.8	23.0	24.8	18.9	17.9	16.4	26.5	13.5	17.2	11.9	26.7	7.9	10.8	12.9	13.7
Mashobra	6.9	18.3	17.9	8.2	5.4	2.5	4.8	2.7	1.6	1.4	7.3	9.2	12.0	8.0	14.5	22.3	22.8	18.1	28.5	35.9	25.4	27.2	13.5	22.6	23.3	17.8	12.6	10.6	15.2	19.1	17.8
Nadaun	11.8	4.9	4.7	0.8	1.0	1.0	0.4	1.3	2.5	13.3	3.5	4.2	6.6	4.5	10.1	14.3	5.7	10.0	16.8	18.2	15.9	8.0	2.2	17.1	7.5	8.5	5.5	2.7	6.2	2.5	3.0
Nahan	6.6	10.3	3.3	1.7	0.9	1.4	0.7	2.7	2.6	1.4	4.0	7.4	17.5	6.9	8.9	12.7	11.6	7.7	20.8	18.1	10.0	11.3	8.2	10.0	9.2	4.7	2.5	6.2	3.5	4.4	7.2
Nichar	1.9	4.4	6.7	2.8	5.3	2.5	4.8	4.2	2.6	3.1	5.2	7.3	12.2	18.0	27.1	17.1	31.0	29.1	30.8	30.9	28.8	22.0	28.4	22.8	32.6	29.6	21.5	16.4	13.7	19.8	17.8

Nurpur	21.1	30.9	5.7	5.6	9.1	45.5	6.0	6.0	8.2	39.5	8.3	6.7	21.6	17.7	27.5	15.0	18.2	15.6	44.5	22.5	21.6	15.7	40.0	17.9	16.8	8.7	38.4	19.3	6.5	12.4	10.1
Pachhad	9.6	10.1	3.1	2.2	2.0	0.7	2.6	2.9	4.1	0.8	5.2	10.6	13.9	5.8	8.7	13.1	14.4	13.1	21.0	24.9	10.7	12.9	14.3	11.6	9.9	8.6	3.8	7.4	15.9	5.3	6.8
Palampur	11.7	12.6	6.3	3.1	2.8	4.0	4.0	2.7	5.9	3.7	12.2	9.3	18.7	16.4	20.3	20.3	31.0	16.4	26.1	35.5	25.4	27.6	19.0	27.0	31.3	14.5	14.7	13.0	12.7	12.2	15.3
Paunta	4.7	2.3	10.2	0.1	0.3	1.3	1.6	1.0	1.5	2.2	2.7	6.9	14.1	4.1	7.1	6.9	4.1	6.0	17.7	17.4	10.0	9.9	6.9	5.9	5.5	4.4	5.5	0.6	1.5	3.3	6.3
Rohru	5.2	8.6	9.6	2.4	4.5	3.2	1.3	3.2	1.6	2.4	5.6	4.2	12.2	8.3	15.3	21.2	18.6	14.3	24.8	22.5	19.7	30.6	15.1	17.6	22.2	16.1	14.1	13.0	16.1	13.4	13.4
Salooni	19.8	18.6	35.5	17.6	21.8	28.7	28.8	28	18.2	66.7	25.1	33.0	52.8	63.7	48.4	46.9	22.9	32.7	51.4	29.0	22.9	38.0	17.3	34.2	37.0	23.0	20.2	18.1	35.2	13.9	21.2
Sangla	17.5	11.0	17.6	9.7	10.2	6.4	5.3	6.9	6.4	6.3	4.8	9.1	7.8	12.2	16.0	13.6	18.8	32.2	16.2	16.7	25.2	17.5	21.6	16.2	9.5	21.5	16.8	23.4	16.7	15.8	11.5
Sarkaghat	4.9	5.3	4.0	1.7	3.4	3.5	1.0	2.3	2.5	3.6	5.9	5.0	8.2	7.3	8.2	14.1	17.4	10.1	11.0	15.2	13.0	15.8	11.7	11.7	15.9	6.9	9.9	8.3	10.1	8.9	11.3
Shimla	7.7	9.6	8.7	1.8	0.9	2.1	1.1	4.6	1.9	2.7	7.4	6.9	10.0	7.6	12.9	21.5	14.2	8.5	24.5	20.2	16.9	20.8	11.3	18.4	17.0	13.6	8.8	13.5	7.8	13.8	14.1
Sundarnagar	22.4	13.0	7.3	11.8	9.0	5.5	6.5	8.3	6.0	2.7	4.9	6.1	7.2	8.7	10.1	8.2	24.5	17.5	9.6	15.9	18.9	18.8	22.8	13.6	19.0	9.3	15.3	10.4	10.9	10.3	11.4
Theog	3.5	7.3	7.6	4.0	1.2	2.1	1.6	2.5	2.0	1.6	6.7	4.7	13.1	7.3	12.7	13.1	16.6	8.0	16.9	25.4	19.1	23.4	16.4	16.2	21.6	10.7	19.4	11.1	10.1	15.4	13.0
Udaipur	6.4	8.3	8.6	8.8	2.3	3.8	2.4	1.6	1.0	4.0	5.1	15.2	5.5	20.5	18.5	20.6	10.6	14.2	46.4	25.8	18.5	28.4	21.7	12.0	25.0	12.9	14.0	14.6	14.7	15.9	9.0
Una	6.0	5.0	3.8	1.2	0.8	3.3	2.3	4.6	5.4	0.9	5.2	7.4	9.4	6.6	9.1	10.1	12.8	7.5	8.8	19.8	11.2	10.0	9.2	11.4	6.9	6.7	3.5	6.2	5.5	5.1	8.8
State	9.0	9.3	7.3	4.0	3.4	5.5	3.6	3.6	3.3	6.4	7.6	7.6	11.7	10.7	13.4	17.6	16.5	13.5	22.7	22.3	17.0	19.7	14.5	17.1	17.3	11.2	10.7	10.0	11.9	10.5	10.9
SD	6.9	5.1	6.0	3.4	4.0	9.4	4.6	4.3	3.2	13.2	4.1	5.1	8.4	9.8	7.9	7.4	6.5	6.6	9.2	6.2	6.2	7.2	7.6	6.8	8.2	5.7	7.3	5.3	7.4	4.8	4.5
CV	76.7	54.5	81.6	86.6	118.1	170.5	126.2	120.2	97.1	206.0	53.7	67.5	72.1	91.5	59.1	41.7	39.5	48.8	40.4	27.8	36.3	36.5	52.5	39.7	47.5	50.9	68.5	53.1	61.9	45.7	41.4

Annexure 1b

Normal weekly rainy days in different wheat growing environments of Himachal Pradesh

Station/ Weeks	40	41	42	43	44	45	46	47	48	49	50	51	52	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12	13	14	15	16	17	18		
Akrot	1	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	1	1	1	1	1	1	0	1	1	1	0	1	0	0	1	0	0	
Arki	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1		
Bajaura	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	2	2	2	2	2	1	2	2	1	1	1	2	1	2	
Banjar	1	0	1	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	2	2	2	2	2	1	2	2	1	1	2	1	1	1	
Berthin	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	1	1	1	1	2	1	1	1	1	1	0	0	0	1	0	0		
Bhoranj	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	1	1	1	1	2	1	1	1	1	1	1	0	1	0	0	0	1		
Chachiot	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	1	1	0	1	0	1	0	1	1	0	0	1	1	1	
Dehra	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	0	1	1		
Dharamshala	1	1	1	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	2	1	1	2	1	1	1	1	2	1	1	1	1	1	1	
Dhaulakuan	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	1	0	1	1	1	0	1	1	1	1	0	1	1	1	1	0	0	0	0	1	
Ghumarwin	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	0	1	1	1	0	1	1	1	1	1	
Hamirpur	0	1	1	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	1	1	1	0	1	1	1	1	1	2	1	2	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	
Jogindanagar	1	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	1	1	2	1	1	2	2	1	2	1	1	1	1	1	0	2	2	1	0	
Jubbal	1	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	2	1	2	1	1	1	2	1	1	1	1	2	2	
Kandaghat	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	
Kangra	1	1	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	1	1	0	1	0	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	
Karsog	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	2	1	2	1	2	1	2	1	1	1	1	1	1	
Kasuli	1	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	
Keylong	0	1	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	2	1	1	1	2	2	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	
Kotkhai	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	
Kumarsain	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	
Malan	1	1	1	0	1	2	0	0	1	2	1	1	1	1	1	1	2	1	2	1	1	1	2	1	1	1	1	2	1	1	1	1	
Mandi	1	1	1	0	1	2	0	0	1	2	1	1	1	1	1	1	2	1	2	1	1	1	2	1	1	1	2	1	1	1	1	1	
Mashobra	1	1	1	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	2	2	2	2	2	1	2	2	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	
Nadaun	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	0	1	1	1	1	1	0	1	0	0	
Nahan	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	0	0	0	0	0	1	
Nichar	0	1	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	1	1	1	2	1	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	1	1	1	2	
Nurpur	1	1	1	1	1	2	1	1	1	2	1	1	2	1	1	1	1	1	2	1	1	1	2	1	1	1	2	1	1	1	1	1	
Pachhad	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	0	0	0	1	0	0		
Palampur	1	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	2	1	1	1	1	1	2	1	1	1	1	1	1	
Paunta	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	1	1	0	0	1	1	1	1	0	0	1	0	1	0	0	0	1	1	
Rohru	0	1	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	1	1	1	1	2	2	1	2	1	1	1	2	1	1	1	1	1	1	2	
Salooni	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	2	1	1	2	2	1	2	1	1	2	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	2	1	1
Sangla	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	
Sarkaghat	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	
Shimla	1	1	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	1	0	1	1	1	1	1	2	1	1	1	1	1	1	2	1	1	1	1	1	1	
Sundarnagar	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	0	0	0	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	
Theog	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	1	1	1	1	1	1	2	1	1	1	1	1	2	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	
Udaipur	1	1	1	1	0	1	0	0	0	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	2	1	1	2	1	1	2	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	
Una	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	0	0	0	0	1		
State	1	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	

Annexure 1c

Normal monthly temperature (°C) of different wheat growing environments of Himachal Pradesh

Week No./stations	Akrot		Bajaura		Berthin		Dhaulakuan		Kangra		Malan		Palampur		Salooni		Shimla		Mean	
	Max.	Min.	Max.	Min.	Max.	Min.	Max.	Min.	Max.	Min.	Max.	Min.	Max.	Min.	Max.	Min.	Max.	Min.	Max.	Min.
Oct	30.9	16.4	27.4	9.0	29.3	14.1	29.7	13.7	28.8	15.8	27.3	15.0	24.8	13.6	25.4	13.6	21.2	11.5	27.2	13.6
Nov	26.8	10.8	23.3	3.5	25.4	7.3	25.9	8.0	24.8	10.0	24.0	10.8	21.1	9.5	23.4	11.9	17.8	8.3	23.6	8.9
Dec	22.2	7.0	18.2	0.7	20.9	4.0	21.9	4.5	20.9	6.2	19.9	7.3	17.6	6.4	20.2	10.1	14.6	5.6	19.6	5.8
Jan	19.2	6.1	15.9	1.0	18.6	3.6	19.5	4.4	18.3	5.2	16.9	5.7	15.2	4.9	18.0	8.1	12.1	3.6	17.1	4.7
Feb	22.1	9.1	17.5	3.4	21.3	6.5	22.3	6.5	20.2	8.2	18.9	7.2	16.6	6.4	16.5	7.0	13.2	4.4	18.7	6.5
Mar	28.0	12.8	21.9	6.0	27.0	9.4	27.5	10.0	25.7	10.7	23.7	10.1	20.9	10.1	19.2	8.0	17.3	7.9	23.5	9.4
Apr	34.5	17.9	26.4	9.1	31.9	12.9	33.8	14.0	30.9	15.0	28.6	13.5	26.1	14.5	20.1	8.3	21.7	12.1	28.2	13.0
May	37.8	22.6	30.4	12.7	35.6	17.4	36.9	19.0	34.6	18.5	33.2	18.2	29.9	18.2	21.1	9.0	25.0	15.6	31.6	16.8

Annexure 1d

Normal monthly rainfall (mm) of different wheat growing stations of Himachal Pradesh

Station	Oct	Nov	Dec	Jan	Feb	Mar	Apr	May	Station	Oct	Nov	Dec	Jan	Feb	Mar	Apr	May
Akrot	25	5	16	40	47	31	23	40	Kumarsain	18	13	23	51	61	57	45	57
Arki	25	12	28	56	66	62	32	48	Malan	26	13	22	70	82	58	30	36
Bajaura	26	19	34	67	105	114	70	73	Mandi	66	56	77	106	83	73	60	88
Banjar	20	16	30	67	86	95	60	65	Mashobra	53	16	30	79	111	88	62	88
Berthin	19	7	20	53	62	55	21	39	Nadaun	22	6	28	41	56	42	18	27
Bhoranj	17	4	15	58	68	50	27	57	Nahan	22	8	31	45	57	38	18	45
Chachiot	16	4	12	37	44	36	30	55	Nichar	16	19	28	110	113	124	78	74
Dehra	25	10	32	55	66	57	28	44	Nurpur	64	71	80	89	105	85	81	66
Dharamshala	43	19	47	93	113	112	60	72	Pachhad	25	11	31	51	66	52	33	34
Dhaulakuan	20	6	28	43	67	37	21	48	Palampur	34	19	45	97	105	108	56	81
Ghumarwin	29	14	26	67	72	58	31	40	Paonta	18	4	27	26	54	26	11	30
Hamirpur	29	13	29	65	81	63	35	55	Rohru	26	13	24	73	90	82	60	52
Jogindernagar	35	12	30	80	87	87	70	39	Salooni	98	115	182	198	135	133	95	66
Jubbal	35	11	37	77	78	83	56	83	Sangla	58	31	30	75	82	76	79	62
Kandaghat	28	13	42	56	75	56	30	44	Sarkaghat	17	11	23	53	50	55	40	61
Kangra	26	17	22	61	74	50	39	27	Shimla	28	10	27	60	76	70	47	69
Karsog	23	15	22	63	73	82	51	58	Sundarnagar	58	31	22	61	59	75	51	60
Kasauli	26	13	28	51	67	64	29	57	Theog	23	9	26	55	76	76	58	68
Keylong	13	17	36	43	78	106	57	38	Udaipur	32	11	30	71	111	93	61	45
Kotkhai	19	9	21	45	61	43	43	68	Una	16	16	23	43	47	40	21	29
Over all mean										30	18	34	66	77	70	45	55
Stan. Dev										17	20	27	29	21	27	20	17
CV (%)										57	113	81	43	28	38	45	31

Annexure 1e

Normal monthly rainy days of different wheat growing stations of Himachal Pradesh

Station	Oct	Nov	Dec	Jan	Feb	Mar	Apr	May	Station	Oct	Nov	Dec	Jan	Feb	Mar	Apr	May
Akrot	2	1	1	3	3	3	2	3	Kumarsain	2	1	2	4	5	5	5	5
Arki	1	1	2	3	5	4	3	3	Malan	2	1	2	4	6	5	3	3
Bajaura	2	2	2	4	7	7	6	6	Mandi	4	3	4	6	6	6	5	6
Banjar	2	2	2	5	6	7	6	7	Mashobra	4	2	2	5	6	7	6	7
Berthin	2	1	1	3	4	4	2	3	Nadaun	1	1	1	3	4	3	2	2
Bhoranj	1	0	1	4	4	3	2	3	Nahan	1	1	2	3	4	3	1	3
Chachiot	0	0	1	2	3	2	2	3	Nichar	2	2	2	5	7	8	6	7
Dehra	2	1	2	4	4	4	2	3	Nurpur	4	4	5	5	5	5	5	4
Dharamshala	3	2	3	6	6	7	5	5	Pachhad	1	1	2	3	4	3	2	2
Dhaulakuan	1	1	1	3	4	3	2	4	Palampur	2	1	2	5	6	6	4	5
Ghumarwin	2	1	1	4	4	4	2	3	Paonta	1	0	2	2	3	2	1	3
Hamirpur	2	1	2	4	6	5	3	5	Rohru	2	1	2	5	6	6	5	5
Jogindernagar	2	1	2	5	6	5	5	3	Salooni	4	5	6	6	6	5	5	4
Jubbal	2	1	3	5	6	7	5	7	Sangla	5	4	3	4	4	5	5	6
Kandaghat	2	1	2	4	5	4	3	4	Sarkaghat	2	1	2	4	4	4	3	5
Kangra	3	1	2	4	5	4	3	3	Shimla	2	1	2	4	5	5	4	6
Karsog	2	1	2	4	5	6	4	5	Sundarnagar	4	3	2	4	4	5	4	4
Kasuli	2	1	2	3	5	4	3	4	Theog	1	1	2	4	5	6	5	5
Keylong	1	2	3	3	5	6	5	4	Udaipur	4	2	3	4	6	6	5	5
Kotkhai	1	1	2	4	5	4	4	6	Una	1	1	1	3	3	3	2	2
Over all mean										2	1	2	4	5	5	4	4
Stan. Dev										1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1
CV (%)										53	72	46	25	21	31	41	33

Crop Management

a. Agro advisories and weather based management for raising wheat crop in rain fed areas

Temperature bears a direct relationship with growth of different crops. The temperature and rainfall forecast is not only useful for harvesting, threshing and other management practices but also for application of various agrochemicals for control of insect pest and weeds. For example, the sowing of crops can commence with the improvement of temperature in extremely cold areas and also with increased soil moisture in dry areas. Increasing ambient temperature increases surface soil temperature and temperature in first few centimetres of soil surface layer determines the germination and emergence of the seeds. No germination takes place under the availability of scarce soil moisture and extremely low or high temperature conditions. Hence, weather forecast plays an extremely useful role in the production and productivity of all crops including wheat. The application of agrochemicals is effective only if the sky is clear (< 1mm daily rainfall) and adequate soil moisture (20-30%) is present in the soil. Higher wind speed more than 8 kmph drifts the agrochemicals away from the target and reduces the efficacy of these chemicals considerably. At the time of sowing or within few days of sowing adequate soil moisture must be present in the soil for proper germination. If the upper surface of the soil is well pulverized, occurrence of 10 mm of rain generally wets soil depth up to 25 -30 cm. Field operations involving manual labour should also be guided through weather forecast as it will improve the efficiency of the farm operations. The application of the weather forecast can really prove useful for increasing the yield of different crops under rain fed and irrigated condition by reducing the cost of production in different crops including wheat.

b. Management before and during sowing

For uniform germination and adequate crop stand wheat crop requires a well pulverized but compact seedbed. To attain desirable seedbed in soils where rice is grown as upland or transplanted, 3-4 ploughings, repeated harrowings, cultivation and planking or laddering are required for raising a good crop of wheat. However, in well-drained loamy, sandy loam and clayey loam soils only 1-2 ploughings, one harrowing, cultivation and planking might be sufficient. Breaking of clods in clayey loam or silty loam soil is a very difficult process as criss-cross mechanical tillage/ploughings is not feasible in the state due to small and terraced fields. In

that case a clod breaker, an implement locally called as '*Bhutann*'(which is one foot long cylindrical strong wooden log narrow and pointed from one end meant to dig the buried clod and flat from the other to crush the clod, with a long strong wooden handle) is used to break the clods. Under rain fed condition, cultivation of wheat is very difficult though other climatic conditions are favourable for its growth.

For management of moisture in the soil for ensuring proper germination, the residual moisture available in the soil after the receding the monsoon is conserved through proper tillage and planking to ensure sufficient seed-soil contact. The experienced farmers of the state also harvest/ capture dew by ploughing the fields and seeding the crop in the evening and planking the same in the early morning. Temperature of soil depends upon air and they go hand in hand. Though higher than ambient, the soil temperatures during winter fall rapidly in the state. In addition soil temperature is variable in different parts of the state due to its varied topography and geographical settings. It has been observed that if ambient temperature is very low then germination of wheat crop is hampered. The early sowing in the state has an overriding advantage of utilizing the residual soil moisture and optimum soil temperature for ensuring proper germination.

Sowing is a major operation for cultivation of wheat. Placing the seeds at proper depth into a soil of proper tilth is called as seeding. It involves selection of varieties, time of seeding, seed rate, method of seeding, seeding depth, spacing etc.

c. Varieties

For raising good crop of wheat only recommended varieties given in the package and practices of CSK HPKV should be grown. For further details for package and practices for *rabi* crops of CSK HPKV should be consulted (www.hillagric.ac.in). In present investigation five varieties HS-490, VL-804, VL-829, VL-892, VL-907 have been used and their varietal characteristics are given below:

Cultivar Characteristics:

Key varietal parameters	Name of varieties				
	HS-490	VL-804	VL-829	VL-892	VL-907
Type of cultivar	National check	National check	National check	National check	National check
Days to maturity	130-150	150-180	180-190	130-150	150-180
Plant height(cm)	105-125	90-125	100-120	100-120	95-125
Suitable sowing time	Late sowing	Timely sowing	Early sowing	Late sowing	Timely sowing

d. Fertilizer applications

All crops including wheat, remove huge amount of nitrogen, phosphate and potash from the soil. Until and unless these removed nutrients are replenished, the crop will suffer acutely, the soil gets depleted, resulting in poor productivity of crop. Therefore, it is essential to supply those nutrients to the soils sufficiently every time when wheat/other crops are grown.

In rain fed areas, complete dose of phosphate and potash and half of nitrogen should be given at the time of sowing through line sowing or *pora* method. The remaining half dose of nitrogen should be given after the rain. In irrigated areas, complete dose of phosphate and potash and half of nitrogen should be given at the time of sowing. The remaining half dose of nitrogen should be given after crown root initiation (CRI) stage. To get the complete benefit of nitrogen it should be applied at adequate soil moisture or after adequate rain/ irrigation.

Application of nitrogen should be planned taking medium range forecast into consideration, if no rain is expected in next 3-5 days only then nitrogen in the form of urea should be applied otherwise severe leaching losses are imminent.

e. Irrigation management

Wheat sown under irrigated condition requires 4-irrigations, depending on the soil and weather conditions. Water requirement of wheat vis-à-vis irrigation also depends upon a particular phase of growth for maximum biomass production. Two stages of the wheat are more critical in respect of moisture stress i.e., i) early CRI stage and tillers formation ii) at flowering to grain filling stages leading to lower yield. Though, adequate moisture must be present all through the growth phases up to maturity and of course dry conditions for the ripening of the grains. Therefore, the first and most important irrigation should be given at CRI stage.

Irrigation depends on the availability of the water, so if water is available only for one irrigation, it should be applied at CRI stage; if available for two irrigations, then should be given

at CRI and late tillering (LT) phase. If water is available for three irrigations, should be given at CRI, LT and flowering stages.

f. Weeds management

Weeds, the unwanted plants do enormous damage to the wheat crop. These weeds directly deplete soil nutrients and moisture and also compete with the crop for light, space, moisture etc. Indirectly they cause damage to the crops by harbouring pests and diseases which also reduce the net returns, by making the harvest and threshing of crop most costly and laborious and by lowering the quality and reducing the value of produce (grains) because of mixture with weed seeds. Weeds cause maximum damage during early crop growth stages. Hence weeding should be done to avoid severe crop weed competition. Weeding in the wheat crop by manual labourers, is the best for the production of higher yield, but it is very labourious, tedious, time consuming and costly affair, besides having the risk of uprooting the crop due to shallow rooting depth of wheat. Therefore, for commercial cultivation it is not feasible. Wheat crop should be kept weed- free, only by using recommended herbicides either ‘broad spectrum’ or ‘selective’ or both. Spray should be planned taking medium range forecast in to considerations discussed in previous sections

Use of herbicides has become quite prevalent in several parts of the country, since it is economical, effective and enables timely control of weeds. Recommended doses of herbicides should be applied for better yields.

g. Management of weather aberrations during different phenophases of wheat in Himachal Pradesh

Under rain fed conditions, during sowing period, if rainfall is delayed by two weeks the seed rate can be increased by 25 percent to compensate loss in plant population. If this delay prolongs for four weeks in addition to seed rate, the rate of fertilizer should also be increased by 25 per cent. During vegetative phase of the crop, harmful effects of dry spell of two consecutive weeks can be minimized by removing weeds, carrying out interculture operations and spraying nutrients. During flowering, in the event of availability of irrigation water, life saving irrigation with foliar spray of nitrogen is highly beneficial to combat dry spell of two consecutive weeks. Under irrigated conditions, if untimely and heavy rain occurs, drain out the excess water from wheat fields during vegetative phase and completely drain off the water during flowering and maturity phase.

Annexure 3

Phenophase- wise accumulated photo thermal units (PTU) taken by different wheat varieties under rain fed and irrigated conditions

Phenological stages	Accumulated photo thermal units							
	5 th November		20 th November		5 th December		20 th December	
	RF	IRR	RF	IRR	RF	IRR	RF	IRR
VL 907								
Emergence	3265	1428	2230	1223	1472	1117	982	817
Tillering	6258	5109	4762	3958	3672	3030	2742	2333
Heading	11963	10906	10983	10527	10289	10886	10774	11532
Grain filling	14939	14401	13738	13281	13054	13551	13763	14270
Phy. maturity	21683	20646	20799	20128	19674	19639	18691	19634
VL 804								
Emergence	3447	1454	2117	1463	1564	1067	979	763
Tillering	6267	4955	4663	3939	3616	2961	2738	2331
Heading	11505	10849	11068	10744	10913	10937	10866	11583
Grain filling	14935	14077	13565	13498	13293	13684	13721	13833
Phy. maturity	21940	20807	20723	19772	19710	19814	18546	18855
VL 829								
Emergence	3308	1506	2207	1228	1545	1040	1272	723
Tillering	6107	5258	4446	3916	3662	2934	4220	2424
Heading	11463	11677	10713	11152	10436	10912	11860	12723
Grain filling	14634	14213	13454	13685	12920	13657	15341	15164
Phy. maturity	21708	20535	20612	20172	19269	19202	22080	21573
VL 892								
Emergence	3394	1513	2053	1355	1497	1010	985	820
Tillering	6287	5285	4752	4020	3600	2959	2740	2347
Heading	11644	10991	10502	10679	10005	10734	10079	11581
Grain filling	14458	14049	13422	13692	12960	13269	12789	14844
Phy. maturity	21612	20252	20665	19835	19500	19056	18535	18831
HS 490								
Emergence	3383	1561	2124	1427	1393	1113	969	679
Tillering	6283	5165	4670	4009	3548	2935	2652	1981
Heading	11995	10582	10884	10606	10190	10558	10501	11338
Grain filling	14937	13895	13562	13054	12759	13495	13114	14171
Phy. maturity	21679	20313	20856	19567	19603	18985	18272	18295
Pooled								
Emergence	3360	1493	2146	1339	1494	1069	1037	760
Tillering	6240	5155	4659	3968	3620	2964	3019	2283
Heading	11714	11001	10830	10742	10367	10805	10816	11751
Grain filling	14781	14127	13548	13442	12997	13531	13746	14457
Phy. maturity	21724	20511	20731	19895	19551	19339	19225	19438

RF- Rain fed, IRR- Irrigated

Annexure 3a

Phenophase- wise accumulative heliothermal units (HTU) taken by different wheat varieties under rain fed and irrigated conditions

Phenological stages	Accumulated heliothermal units							
	5 th November		20 th November		5 th December		20 th December	
	RF	IRR	RF	IRR	RF	IRR	RF	IRR
VL 907								
Emergence	2515	1133	1696	952	1115	844	698	619
Tillering	4682	3964	3463	2978	2515	2163	1756	1517
Heading	7862	7351	6855	6664	6190	6452	6091	6565
Grain filling	9534	9147	8361	8061	7620	7867	7882	8101
Phy. maturity	13401	12877	12571	12192	11658	11672	10925	11507
VL 804								
Emergence	2650	1156	1615	1155	1186	802	708	577
Tillering	4690	3877	3424	2945	2510	2093	1773	1552
Heading	7578	7311	6990	6801	6466	6481	6106	6605
Grain filling	9463	8947	8268	8169	7724	7967	7896	7854
Phy. maturity	13586	12921	12552	11957	11661	11733	10807	11012
VL 829								
Emergence	2543	1177	1672	953	1181	784	676	612
Tillering	4568	4075	3260	2947	2468	2094	1786	1588
Heading	7559	7795	6740	7071	6251	6483	5976	6770
Grain filling	9312	9089	8190	8295	7531	7944	7526	7995
Phy. maturity	13440	12744	12447	12158	11356	11349	10940	11353
VL 892								
Emergence	2610	1193	1643	982	1137	752	700	626
Tillering	4691	4106	3454	3026	2483	2123	1778	1575
Heading	7661	7408	6657	6607	6041	6517	5690	6581
Grain filling	9230	8937	8293	8048	7547	7775	7262	8439
Phy. maturity	13369	12645	12555	11924	11568	11333	10808	10999
HS 490								
Emergence	2609	1237	1620	1128	1049	845	704	511
Tillering	4692	4015	3424	3011	2452	2113	1742	1337
Heading	7864	7169	6855	6723	6136	6301	5964	6468
Grain filling	9467	8860	8261	7993	7432	7895	7459	8043
Phy. maturity	13404	12656	12605	11805	11630	11291	10595	10648
Pooled								
Emergence	2585	1179	1649	1034	1133	805	697	589
Tillering	4665	4008	3405	2981	2486	2117	1767	1514
Heading	7705	7407	6819	6773	6217	6447	5965	6598
Grain filling	9401	8996	8275	8113	7571	7890	7605	8086
Phy. maturity	13440	12769	12546	12007	11574	11476	10815	11104

RF- Rain fed, IRR- Irrigated

